

22RPT03 MultiFixRad

Deliverable D1: Training materials on the temperature scale realisation in ITS-90 and the MeP-K for use in the radiation thermometry community for later training

Organisation name of the lead participant for the deliverable:

Český Metrologický Institut

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Deliverable Cover Sheet

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**METROLOGY
PARTNERSHIP**

EURAMET

Glossary

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1 Summary

This deliverable consists of three presentations given at a training session during the project kickoff. They cover (i) general principles of radiation thermometry and some of the considerations and work performed within the Consultative Committee for Thermometry (CCT) in the years leading up to the redefinition of the Kelvin in 2019; (ii) the construction of high temperature fixed points, including the basics of alloys, several difficulties that can arise without proper caution, and the design solutions that LNE-Cnam finally decided to use to ensure robust and reliable fixed points; and (iii) interpolation/extrapolation schemes in radiation thermometry and how a scale can be constructed from measuring the response of a radiation thermometer at 1, 2, 3 or more fixed points.

Radiation thermometry combines classical radiometry (the light detection and intensity quantification, which also requires optics), statistical physics, statistical modelling and data fitting, and some elementary metallurgy. This is a wide scope, which is reflected in the length and the ambitions of the presentations.

Appendix 1. Fundamentals of radiation thermometry and the mise-en-pratique of the kelvin at high temperature

*Liberté
Égalité
Fraternité*

FUNDAMENTALS OF RADIATION THERMOMETRY AND THE MISE- EN-PRACTIQUE OF THE KELVIN AT HIGH TEMPERATURE

Mohamed SADLI

LNE-Cnam

MultiFixRad Knowledge Transfer Workshop

PRAGUE 14-15 JUNE 2023

- Introduction
- Radiation thermometry, general introductory theory and practice
- The mise-en-pratique of the kelvin at high temperature
- Realisation of the international temperature scale of 1990
- Thermodynamic temperature (radiance method)
- HTFPs and assigned thermodynamic temperatures
- Dissemination of thermodynamic temperature
- Conclusion

The new definition of the kelvin allows the use of thermodynamic temperature for the realisation of the unit and its dissemination.

There are several possibilities to realise the kelvin at HT:

- ITS-90 extrapolation from Cu, Ag or Au
- Measuring thermodynamic temperature (with radiometric traceability to the cryogenic radiometer)
- Using high-temperature fixed points with assigned thermodynamic temperatures to interpolate/extrapolate T

➤ We need to know $T-T_{90}$ to avoid a « double system » and confusion

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**Any object at a temperature T emits energy by radiation.
The aim of radiation thermometry is to link temperature
to thermal energy**

- Radiance temperature
- Traceability to the ITS-90?

THERMAL RADIATION

Radiation is distributed in space and only part of it is collected:

Radiance :

$$\text{solid angle: } d\Omega_s = \frac{dA_r}{D^2}$$

$$\text{radiance: } L = \frac{d^2\phi}{dA_s \cdot d\Omega_s}$$

Planck's law for radiation relates the spectral density of radiance of a blackbody to its temperature T and to the wavelength:

$$L_{\lambda, \text{CN}}(\lambda, T) = \frac{2 \cdot h \cdot c^2}{\lambda^5 \cdot \left[e^{\frac{h \cdot c}{\lambda \cdot k \cdot T}} - 1 \right]} = \frac{C_1 \cdot \lambda^{-5}}{e^{\frac{C_2}{\lambda \cdot T}} - 1}$$

Boltzmann constant inside! It's a primary method!

SPECTRAL DENSITY OF RADIANCE

EXITANCE (STEFAN-BOLTZMANN)

Total exitance is obtained by integrating over the whole spectral range :

$$M_{\text{CN}} = \int_0^{\infty} M_{\lambda, \text{CN}}(\lambda) \cdot d\lambda = \int_0^{\infty} \pi \cdot L_{\lambda, \text{CN}}(\lambda, T) \cdot d\lambda = \sigma \cdot T^4$$

where, $\sigma = \frac{2 \pi^5 k^4}{15 c^2 h^3} = 5,670 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ W.m}^{-2} \cdot \text{K}^{-4}$

BLACKBODY

Planck's law for radiation relates the spectral density of radiance of a blackbody to its temperature T and to the wavelength:

$$L_{\lambda, \text{CN}}(\lambda, T) = \frac{2 \cdot h \cdot c^2}{\lambda^5 \cdot \left[e^{\frac{h \cdot c}{\lambda \cdot k \cdot T}} - 1 \right]} = \frac{C_1 \cdot \lambda^{-5}}{e^{\frac{C_2}{\lambda \cdot T}} - 1}$$

THERMAL RADIATION

Spectral and spacial distributions of radiation emitted from a surface

EMISSIVITY

The notion of blackbody is a theoretical and ideal case:

« **no surface can emits as much radiation as a blackbody at the same temperature** »

Emissivity can be defined as:

$$\textit{Emissivity of a surface} = \frac{\textit{radiation emitted by the surface}}{\textit{radiation emitted by a perfect blackbody}}$$

Provided the surface and the blackbody are at the same temperature and seen in the same optical and spectral conditions.

DIRECTIONAL EMISSIVITY

Integrated emissivity (complement to 1 of reflectivity $\rho(\lambda, T)$ for opaque materials) depends on the geometry of the cavity

Cylindrical cavity :

$$\varepsilon_c \approx 1 - \rho(\lambda, T) \cdot \frac{r^2}{l^2}$$

$$\varepsilon_c \text{ close to } 1 \text{ if } \frac{r}{l} \ll 1$$

TYPICAL MEASUREMENT SCHEME : FLUXES

- Contribution of ambient radiation by reflection on the source surface
- Transmission of the radiation from the back through the target
- Absorption of the radiation in the intermediary medium (air, gases, window,...)

WHY USING RADIATION THERMOMETRY ?

High temperatures (no contact)...

But also :

Health (*ear thermometers*)

Meteorology, (*clouds temperature measurement: 0,3 °C accuracy seeked*)

Archeology et geophysics, (*detecting thermal differences on earth due to burried structures*)

Environment (*waste burning temperature control*)

Agronomy (*verfifying mathematical models of photosynthesis at temperatures from 2°C to 10°C measured with an accuracy better than 1 °C*)

Food storage and transportation (*non contact for hygiene reasons*)

Extrusion of aluminum (*temperature control is important for the quality and reproducibility of the process*) ...

EMISSIVITY ERRORS

Temperature error due to a **10 % over-estimation** of the emissivity at different wavelengths and temperatures

ABSORPTION OF RADIATION BY WINDOWS

Transmission of the window should be very high in the spectral region of interest.

ABSORPTION DUE TO ATMOSPHERIC GASES

REFLECTION ERRORS

Kirchoff's law $\varepsilon + r + \tau = 1$ predicts that the ambient radiation reflected on a surface induces an error which is bigger if the emissivity is smaller.

$$\frac{1}{e^{\frac{c_2}{\lambda \cdot T_{\text{mesurée}}} - 1}} = \varepsilon(\lambda) \cdot \frac{1}{e^{\frac{c_2}{\lambda \cdot T_{\text{source}}} - 1}} + (1 - \varepsilon(\lambda)) \cdot \frac{1}{e^{\frac{c_2}{\lambda \cdot T_{\text{four}}} - 1}}$$

Exp: a surface with emissivity of 0.92 whose temperature is 50°C measured inside a furnace at 175 °C with a pyrometer working at 4.3 μm is wrong by $\Delta T = + 30 \text{ °C}$

Error $\Delta T \searrow$ when $\varepsilon \nearrow$ et $T_{\text{furnace}} - T_{\text{source}} \searrow$

- ✓ Influence of ambient radiation
- ✓ Effects of optical aberrations
- ✓ Diffraction inside the pyrometer

Calibration of a pyrometer should be done at a reference source size

Temperature acts on pyrometers:

- On the gain and zero signal
- Inner radiation changes with temperature
 - ↪ Pyrometers are temperature controlled
 - ↪ Characterisations, corrections

Humidity in the ambient air can affect the absorption of the radiation

- ↪ Choosing a detector working in an absorption-free pyrometer
- ↪ Characterisations, corrections

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THE PREVIOUS KELVIN DEFINITION

“the kelvin, unit of thermodynamic temperature, is the fraction $1/273.16$ of the thermodynamic temperature of the triple point of water” (isotopic composition of water defined)

THE NEW KELVIN DEFINITION

The kelvin, symbol k , is the si unit of thermodynamic temperature. it is defined by taking the fixed numerical value of the boltzmann constant k to be $1.380\ 649 \times 10^{-23}$ when expressed in the unit $j\ k^{-1}$, which is equal to $kg\ m^2\ s^{-2}\ k^{-1}$, where the kilogram, metre and second are defined in terms of h , c and δV_{CS} . (si brochure 9th edition)

CONDITIONS FOR THE REDEFINITION SET IN 2014

To achieve this new definition without changing the value and intensity of the kelvin and without degrading the uncertainty of the realisation of the unit, the Consultative Committee for Thermometry (CCT) at its 2014 general meeting stated two conditions:

- **The relative standard uncertainty on the determination of the Boltzmann constant k had to be less than $1 \cdot 10^{-6}$;**
- **The determination of k had to be based on at least two fundamentally independent methods, the results of at least one of which are known to better than $3 \cdot 10^{-6}$ relative uncertainty.**

Determining Boltzmann's constant was a prerequisite for this redefinition.

NOTE: the thermodynamic temperature is independent of the concept of temperature scale. It derives from a physical law that makes it possible to determine the temperature from other temperature-independent parameters and physical phenomena.

Thermometer

Thermodynamic relation

Constant volume gas thermometer: Pressure, P , and volume, V , of an ideal gas versus number of molecules, n , and temperature.

$$PV = nkT$$

Acoustic gas thermometer: Speed of sound, u , versus specific heat ratio, γ , molecular mass, m , and temperature.

$$u^2 = \frac{\gamma kT}{m}$$

Dielectric constant gas thermometer: Pressure, P , dielectric constant, ϵ_r , molar electric polarizability A_ϵ , and temperature.

$$\frac{(\epsilon_r - 1)}{(\epsilon_r + 2)} = \frac{PA_\epsilon}{N_A kT}$$

Refractive index gas thermometer: Pressure, P , refractive index, n , molar electric polarizability A_ϵ , molar magnetic polarizability A_μ , and temperature.

$$\frac{(n^2 - 1)}{(n^2 + 2)} = P \frac{(A_\epsilon + A_\mu)}{N_A kT}$$

Total radiation thermometer: Total radiance, L , versus temperature.

$$L = \frac{2\pi^5 k^4}{15c^2 h^3} T^4$$

Spectral-band radiation thermometer: Spectral radiance, L_λ , versus wavelength, λ , and temperature.

$$L_\lambda = \frac{2hc^2}{\lambda^5} \left[\exp\left(\frac{hc}{\lambda kT}\right) - 1 \right]^{-1}$$

Doppler broadening thermometer: Line width $\Delta\nu$, versus line frequency ν_0 , molecular mass, m , and temperature.

$$\Delta\nu = \sqrt{\frac{2kT}{mc^2}} \nu_0$$

Noise thermometer: Mean square noise voltage $\overline{V_T^2}$ versus real part of impedance, Z , bandwidth, Δf , and temperature.

$$\overline{V_T^2} = 4kT \operatorname{Re}(Z) \Delta f$$

QUALIFIED DETERMINATIONS OF K

Laboratory (year)	Method	Relative Std-unc (10^{-6})
LNE-Cnam (2017)	AGT	0,6
NPL (2017)	AGT	0,7
LNE-Cnam (2015)	AGT	1,0
INRIM (2015)	AGT	1,1
LNE-Cnam (2011)	AGT	1,4
NIST (1988)	AGT	1,8
PTB (2017)	DCGT	1,9
NIM (2017)	AGT	2,0
NIM/NIST (2017)	JNT	2,7
LNE-Cnam (2009)	AGT	2,7
NPL (2010)	AGT	3,2

$$k = 1.380\ 649\ 03(51) \times 10^{-23} \text{ J K}^{-1}$$

$$k = 1.380\,649 \times 10^{-23} \text{ J K}^{-1}$$

THE MISE-EN-PRATIQUE OF THE DEFINITION OF THE KELVIN (MEP-K-19)

CIPM recommendation 1 CI-2005 “approve in principle the preparation of **new definitions** and ***mises en pratiques*** of the kilogram, the ampere and the kelvin.....”

A *mise en pratique* is a document that guides the user from the kelvin definition based on k to a practical (laboratory) realisation of the unit

Realisation and dissemination of temperature will be regulated by the *MEP-K-19* (and updates)

THE MEP-K-19 CONTENT

The definition of the kelvin

Definition of terms related to primary thermometry especially

absolute primary thermometry – no fixed points

Relative primary thermometry – fixed points with explicit T

Criteria for inclusion of a thermodynamic method

Outline of primary thermometry methods for realising the kelvin based on fundamental laws of physics [acoustic gas thermometry, radiometry, dielectric constant gas thermometry, refractive index gas thermometry, johnson noise thermometry]

Defined temperature scales, ITS-90, PLTS-2000

Supplementary information: example, consensus values of $T-T_{90}$ & $T-T_{2000}$

$$T - T_{90}$$

T directly linked to the thermodynamic state of the matter → kinetic energy of the molecules
T directly linked to the boltzmann constant, thus to the **new definition of the kelvin**
Does not require using predefined techniques, as stated in *mep-k*

Int J Thermophys (2011) 32:12–25
DOI 10.1007/s10765-011-0922-1

Present Estimates of the Differences Between Thermodynamic Temperatures and the ITS-90

J. Fischer · M. de Podesta · K. D. Hill ·
M. Moldover · L. Pitre · R. Rusby ·
P. Steur · O. Tamura · R. White · L. Wolber

Ongoing Work (CCT
WG C-Th)

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**ITS-90 realisation by
radiation thermometry**

The text of the ITS-90 states:

Above the freezing point of silver the temperature T_{90} is defined by the equation:

$$\frac{L_{\lambda}(T_{90})}{L_{\lambda}[T_{90}(X)]} = \frac{\exp(c_2[\lambda T_{90}(X)]^{-1}) - 1}{\exp(c_2[\lambda T_{90}]^{-1}) - 1} \quad (1)$$

where $T_{90}(X)$ refers to any one of the silver $\{T_{90}(\text{Ag})=1234.93 \text{ K}\}$, gold $\{T_{90}(\text{Au})=1337.33 \text{ K}\}$ or copper $\{T_{90}(\text{Cu})=1357.77 \text{ K}\}$ freezing points, $L_{\lambda}(T_{90})$ and $L_{\lambda}[T_{90}(X)]$ are the spectral concentrations of the radiance of a blackbody at the wavelength (in vacuo) λ at T_{90} and at $T_{90}(X)$ respectively, and $c_2=0.014388 \text{ m}\cdot\text{K}$.

Extrapolation from a fixed point to high temperatures requires (at least):

- the relative spectral responsivity (non-monochromatic)
- the linearity (current-to-voltage converter and detector imperfections)
- the size of source effect (optical imperfections)

Thermodynamic temperature measurement requires the knowledge of the absolute spectral responsivity $S(\lambda)$ and the determination of the coefficient α (geometrical extent, emissivity, SSE, amplification gain ...)

$$R = \alpha \int_0^{\infty} S(\lambda) \cdot L_{\lambda}(\lambda, T) \cdot d\lambda$$

The temperature to determine can be expressed relatively to a reference (fixed point) by Planck's Law in ratio: ITS-90

Measurements are simplified:

- same geometrical extent
- ratio of the amplification gains only
- relative spectral responsivity
- ...

Temperature references : fixed point Cu or Ag (in-house made cells)

- ✓ Temperature drop (correction)
- ✓ Emissivity of the cavity ($\varepsilon = 0,9996(1)$)
@ 650 nm corresponds to 32 mK correction (± 8 mK) at the copper point (1357.77 K)

Measuring instrument : monochromator-based radiance comparator or narrow-band radiation thermometer (2 RTs, 6 wavelengths)

$$R_{Ref} = \alpha \int_0^{\infty} S(\lambda) \cdot L_{\lambda}(\lambda, T_{Ref}) \cdot d\lambda$$

$$R_E = \alpha' \int_0^{\infty} S(\lambda) \cdot L_{\lambda}(\lambda, T_E) \cdot d\lambda$$

$$\frac{L_{\lambda}(T_E)}{L_{\lambda}(T_{Ref})} = \frac{\exp\left[\frac{c_2}{\lambda T_{Ref}}\right] - 1}{\exp\left[\frac{c_2}{\lambda T_E}\right] - 1} = \frac{R_E}{R_{Ref}}$$

Base parameters:

- Spectral responsivity
- Size-of source effect
- Linearity

LNE-CNAM FACILITIES

Chino
IR-R80

Vega
HTBB
3200 pg

Ag

Cu

radiancemeter

LP3

Radiance
comparator

REALISATION OF THE ITS-90: FURNACE

Fixed point (Ag or Cu) in a 3-zone-furnace

WHY A THREE-ZONE FURNACE?

THERMAL EFFECTS

THERMAL EFFECTS

THERMAL EFFECTS

EFFECT OF THE TEMPERATURE GRADIENT ON THE PLATEAU

Cu FIXED POINT: 1357,77 K

Calibration of a standard pyrometer

- Reference temperature (fixed point)
- Spectral responsivity (relative), Linearity, SSE – check stability

Calibration of a W strip lamp

- Good stability if you don't over-use the lamp
- Complex procedure (wavelength, alignment,..)
- But lamps not available anymore and superseded by RTs

Transfer the ITS-90 on HTFPs

- Dissemination over a large range of temperature
- But needs good skills in operation and uncertainty analysis

RADIATION THERMOMETER: KE LP3

$$R = \alpha \int_0^{\infty} S(\lambda) \cdot L_{\lambda}(\lambda, T) \cdot d\lambda$$

RADIANCE COMPARATOR

field stop and entrance slit of the monochromator (1), exit slit of the monochromator (2), precision diffraction grating (3), entrance pupil (4), pupil (5), photodiode (6), current to voltage converter (7), voltmeter (8), alignment laser (9), gold mirrors (10 to 22)

NEED OF A TRANSFER VARIABLE TEMP. BLACKBODY

If both pyrometers work at the (exact) same wavelength, no need to know the emissivity: same radiance temperature!
It is almost NEVER the case!

Integrated emissivity (complement to 1 of reflectivity $\rho(\lambda, T)$ for *opaque materials*) depends on the geometry of the cavity

Cylindrical cavity :

$$\varepsilon_c \approx 1 - \rho(\lambda, T) \cdot \frac{r^2}{l^2}$$

$$\varepsilon_c \text{ close to } 1 \text{ if } \frac{r}{l} \ll 1$$

Emissivity of your cavity must be estimated (commercially available softwares, material emissivity, temperature distribution)

See: O. Kozlova et al. International Journal of Thermophysics 36(8), 2015 DOI: 10.1007/s10765-015-1867-6

TUNGSTEN STRIP LAMPS

Calibration by determination of the current in the strip at a known radiance temperature (at a given wavelength)

Sources of uncertainty:

Base temperature

Current

Drift

Emissivity

Positioning

Quality of polynomial fit

Scale realization

Transmission of window

...

Considering uncertainties (CCT document 2002)

scheme 1:

- the fixed-point calibration is transferred to a reference tungsten strip lamp; this implies the determination of a current value on the lamp corresponding to a radiance temperature equal to the fixed-point temperature;
- a series of temperatures T_{90} are established and maintained on the lamp by measurement of radiance ratios; if necessary, the radiance ratios are adjusted for the non-linearity of the thermometer; this leads to the availability of a series of current and radiance temperature values; a polynomial interpolation equation can be calculated to relate temperature to current in a continuous way

scheme 2:

- the fixed-point calibration is transferred to a reference tungsten strip lamp;
- temperatures T_{90} of any source are determined according to the defining equation of the ITS-90 by measuring the signal ratios between the source at T_{90} and the reference lamp at the fixed-point temperature; if necessary, the signal ratios are adjusted for the non-linearity of the thermometer.

scheme 3:

- the fixed-point calibration is maintained on the thermometer. The output signal is assumed to be representative of $T_{90}(X)$;
- a series of temperatures T_{90} are established as a function of the output signals of the thermometer. Signal ratios with respect to $T_{90}(X)$ are calculated and, if necessary, adjusted for the non-linearity of the thermometer.

<https://www.bipm.org/documents/20126/28438732/working-document-ID-775/b5219f09-2504-ec12-724b-32374500575a>

INTERNATIONAL TEMPERATURE SCALE ITS-90, UNCERTAINTIES

Considering uncertainties (CCT document 2002)

Source of uncertainty		Scheme 1	Scheme 2	Scheme 3
Fixed-point calibration	Impurities			
	Emissivity			
	Temperature drop			
	Plateau identification			
	Repeatability			
Spectral responsivity	Wavelength			
	Reference detector			
	Scattering, Polarisation			
	Repeatability of calibration			
	Drift			
	Out-of-band-transmittance			
	Interpolation and Integration			
Output signal	SSE			
	Non-linearity			
	Drift			
	Ambient conditions			
	Gain ratios			
	Repeatability			
Lamp	Current			
	Drift, Stability			
	Base and ambient temperature			
	Positioning			
	Polynomial fit			

CCT document 2002: spectral responsivity

Figure 1: Simulation of result expected if thermometer is calibrated with a monochromator source with a triangular slit function, rather than with a laser. Real laser calibration shown as dark blue line. The lines are only for connecting the symbols. (Note that the term 'bandwidth' in the figure refers to the monochromator not the filter bandwidth).

SSE OF A RADIATION THERMOMETER

The SSE can be measured by a :

- Direct method, by measuring the radiance of the source with the pyrometer for different source diameters (problem : stability of the source, for sensitive pyrometers ...)
- Indirect method, by measuring the radiance around the target (more sensitive)
- Scanning method, by measuring out of the source (not limited in size, precise but more complex)

SSE OF A RT : INDIRECT METHOD

SSE OF A RT : INDIRECT METHOD

SSE OF A RT : INDIRECT METHOD

$$SSE_d = \frac{R_{center}}{R_{source}}$$

LINEARITY OF THE RADIANCE COMPARATOR

Figure 12. Linearity correction (black spots) and uncertainty at $k = 1$ (error bars) related to the radiance comparator for its usual measuring range. The blackbody temperature, expressed in °C, are indicated above the error bars.

Table 5. Voltage-to-current converter gain ratios of the radiance comparator, relative uncertainty and stability over one year.

Converter gain	9/8	9/7	8/7	8/6	7/6	7/5	6/5
Ratio (07/2017)	10.1339	100.616	9.928 48	99.2761	9.999 16	100.003	10.0012
Relative uncertainty ($k = 1$)	1.5×10^{-6}	1.0×10^{-5}	2.5×10^{-5}	1.0×10^{-5}	2.5×10^{-5}	2.0×10^{-5}	1.0×10^{-5}
Stability over 1 year	1.0×10^{-3}		-8.5×10^{-4}		6.3×10^{-5}		

CCT document 2002

Figure 5: Standard uncertainty in the ITS-90 realisation at normal and best accuracy level

Since 2002 progress was made on radiation thermometers and lamps have (almost) completely disappeared.

CCT-K10 results showed huge improvements...

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RADIANCE METHOD AT LNE-CNAM

3) Measurement of the (absolute) radiance of the FP at $\lambda_{comp} = \lambda_{laser}$

IOP Publishing | Bureau International des Poids et Mesures
 Metrologia 53 (2016) 945–955
 doi:10.1088/0026-1394/53/3/945

A reference radiance-meter system for thermodynamic temperature measurements

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 O Kozlova¹, J-M Coutin¹ and M Sadji¹

HIGH-TEMPERATURE FIXED POINTS

THERMODYNAMIC TEMPERATURE ASSIGNMENT TO HTFPs AT LNE-Cnam

Main uncertainty components mK

Fixed point	Cu	Co-C	Pt-C	Re-C
Radiance	60	83	132	246
Comparison	28	38	67	127
FP / HTFP	17	30	28	52

T values and std uncertainties

Point fixe	T / K	u_T / mK
Cu	1357,86	68
Co-C	1597,4	96
Pt-C	2011,4	150
Re-C	2747,8	280

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Extrapolation to high temperature uncertainty

$$\left(\frac{U_T}{T}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{T \cdot \lambda_0}{C_2}\right)^2 \left(\frac{U_L}{L}\right)^2$$

For $n = 1$ (*ITS-90*), the thermodynamic uncertainty associated with the gold-point temperature is not included.
 For $n = 2$, the Au and WC-C fixed points were used
 For $n = 3$, the Au, Pt-C (1738 °C), and WC-C points were used

**G. Machin · P. Bloembergen · K. Anhalt ·
 J. Hartmann · M. Sadli · P. Saunders ·
 E. Woolliams · Y. Yamada · H. Yoon**
 Int J Thermophys (2010) 31:1779–1788

HTFPs: ASSIGNED THERMODYNAMIC TEMPERATURES (InK 2012-2015)

PHILOSOPHICAL
TRANSACTIONS A

rsta.royalsocietypublishing.org

Research

Cite this article: Woolliams ER *et al.* 2016 Thermodynamic temperature assignment to the point of inflection of the melting curve of high-temperature fixed points. *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. A* **374**: 20150044. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2015.0044>

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One contribution of 16 to a Theo Murphy meeting issue 'Towards implementing the new kelvin'.

Subject Areas:
thermodynamics

Keywords:
high-temperature fixed points,
thermodynamic temperature, thermometry,
temperature scale, kelvin, eutectics

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Electronic supplementary material is available at <http://dx.doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2015.0044> or via <http://rsta.royalsocietypublishing.org>.

Thermodynamic temperature assignment to the point of inflection of the melting curve of high-temperature fixed points

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Results of InK WP1

	T	u(T)(k=1)
Cobalt	1597.475	0.075
[Cobalt]	1597.430	0.074
Platinum	2011.502	0.110
Rhenium	2747.902	0.228

[] indicates non equilibrium values

The equilibrium liquidus temperatures of rhenium-carbon, platinum-carbon and cobalt-carbon eutectic alloys.

D. H. Lowe¹, A. D. W. Todd², R. Van den Bossche³, P. Bloembergen⁴, K. Anhalt⁵, M. Ballico⁶, F. Bourson⁷, S. Briaudeau⁷, J. Campos⁸, M.G. Cox¹, D. del Campo⁹, M.R. Dury¹, V. Gavrilov¹⁰, I. Grigoryeva¹⁰, M.L. Hernanz⁸, F. Jahan⁶, B. Khlevnoy¹⁰, V. Khromchenko¹¹, X. Lu⁴, G. Machin¹, J.M. Mantilla⁹, M.J. Martin⁹, H.C. McEvoy¹, B. Rougié⁷, M. Sadli⁷, S.G.R. Salim⁷, N. Sasajima¹², D.R. Taubert⁴, E. van der Ham⁶, T. Wang⁴, D. Wei⁴, A. Whittam¹, B. Wilthan⁵, D.J. Woods², J.T. Woodward¹¹, E.R. Woolliams¹, Y. Yamada¹², Y. Yamaguchi¹², H.W. Yoon¹¹, Z. Yuan⁵

- In-use uncertainties to be accounted for:

Report from the CCT Task Group for Non-Contact Thermometry HTFP Uncertainties (CCT TG-NCTh-HTFPU)

A.D.W. Todd (NRC), K. Anhalt (PTB), P. Bloembergen (NIM), B. Khlevnoy (VNIIOFI), D.H. Lowe (NPL), G. Machin (NPL), M. Sadli (LNE-Cnam), and N. Sasajima (NMIJ).

T ASSIGNMENT TO THE PHASE TRANSITIONS (F_{E-C} , P_{D-C} , R_{U-C} , W_{C-C}) – REAL-K JRP

➤ Circulation of the cells in two loops:

- Loop A: PTB, CEM, LNE-Cnam, NPL
- Loop B: (VNIIOFI), TUBITAK-UME, NIM, (INRIM)

🕒 Timetable: early fall 2021 – late winter 2022

➤ Measurement of the thermodynamic temperature of the circulating cells

- Absolute T measurement (a radiation thermometer calibrated in thermodynamic temperature values) at PTB, NIM, CEM, Tubitak UME and LNE-Cnam
- Relative T measurement (using high-temperature fixed points with – previously – assigned T) at NPL, CEM, LNE-Cnam and Tubitak UME

➤ Derive phase transition temperatures from radiance temperatures of the cells (emissivity and temperature drop corrections)

➤ Determination of the (weighted) mean temperature for each phase transition

➤ Account for thermal effects

ASSIGNING THERMODYNAMIC TEMPERATURES TO THE PHASE TRANSITION OF Fe-C

Iron-carbon

	POI	LIQ	u(POI)	u(LIQ)
CNAM	1426.69	1427.03	0.1	0.1
CEM	1426.65	1426.74	0.11	0.11
NIM	1426.78		0.08	
NPL	1426.761	1426.842	0.049	0.055
UME	1426.702	1426.797	0.087	0.087
PTB	1426.343		0.127	0.127

Weighted mean :

$$w_i = 1/u_i^2$$

$$Var(x)_{wtd} = (s_x^2)_{wtd} = \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i x_i^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i} - (\bar{x}_{wtd})^2 \right) \frac{n}{n-1}$$

for standard deviation $(s_x)_{wtd}$ with uncertainty in the mean $(s_x)_{wtd}/\sqrt{n}$

	Fe-C	U(Fe-C)
UWM	1426.707	0.10

	Fe-C	U(Fe-C)
UWM	1426.834	0.08

ASSIGNING THERMODYNAMIC TEMPERATURES TO THE PHASE TRANSITION OF Pd-C

Palladium-carbon

	POI	LIQ	u(POI)	u(LIQ)
CNAM	1765.06	1765.3	0.126	0.126
CEM	1765.31	1765.35	0.165	0.165
NIM	1765.07		0.160	
NPL	1764.962	1765.064	0.091	0.096
UME	1764.952	1765.104	0.174	0.174
PTB	1764.872		0.220	

Point-of-inflection

	Pd-C	U(Pd-C)
UWM	1765.032	0.110

Liquidus

	Pd-C	U(Pd-C)
UWM	1765.131	0.124

ASSIGNING THERMODYNAMIC TEMPERATURES TO THE PHASE TRANSITION OF Ru-C

Ruthenium-carbon

	POI	LIQ	u(POI)	u(LIQ)
CNAM	2227.01	2227.17	0.192	0.192
CEM	2227.28	2227.31	0.270	0.270
NIM	2226.99		0.245	
NPL	2227.07	2227.111	0.200	0.200
UME	2226.769	2226.846	0.248	0.248
PTB	2226.619		0.270	

Point-of-inflection

	Ru-C	U(Ru-C)
UWM	2226.95	0.204

Liquidus

	Ru-C	U(Ru-C)
UWM	2227.081	0.169

ASSIGNING THERMODYNAMIC TEMPERATURES TO THE PHASE TRANSITION OF WC-C

Tungsten carbide-carbon

	POI	LIQ	u(POI)	u(LIQ)
CNAM	3020.94	3021.02	0.355	0.355
CEM	3020.6	3020.7	0.500	0.500
NIM	3020.43		0.400	
NPL	3021.077	3021.215	0.511	0.522
UME	3020.451	3020.474	0.579	0.579
PTB	3020.76		0.470	

PROVISIONAL RESULTS

Point-of-inflection

	WC-C	U(WC-C)
UWM	3020.726	0.218

Liquidus

	WC-C	U(WC-C)
UWM	3020.726	0.375

- Introduction
- Radiation thermometry, general introductory theory and practice
- The mise-en-pratique of the kelvin at high temperature
- Realisation of the international temperature scale of 1990
- Thermodynamic temperature (radiance method)
- HTFPs and assigned thermodynamic temperatures
- **Dissemination of thermodynamic temperature**
- Conclusion

In InK WP2 trials of dissemination through :

- Instruments (radiation thermometer or filter radiometer)
- High temperature fixed points

PHILOSOPHICAL TRANSACTIONS A

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Research

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Dissemination of thermodynamic temperature above the freezing point of silver

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D. H. Lowe², J. M. Mantilla Amor⁴, M. J. Martin⁴,
H. C. McEvoy², M. Ojanen-Saloranta⁶, Ö. Pehlivan⁵,
B. Rougié¹ and S. G. R. Salim^{1,7}

DISSEMINATION OF T (RTS/FR)

Agreement within 1 K over the whole temperature range

Figure 7. Thermodynamic temperatures measured with three radiation thermometers calibrated by LNE-Cnam, CEM and PTB and with a MIKES filter radiometer. Uncertainties are expressed with a coverage factor $k = 2$. (Online version in colour.)

DISSEMINATION AT HIGH TEMPERATURE (Re-C POINT)

Agreement within 0.8 K
at Re-C and better at
Co-C and Pt-C

Figure 5. The reported melting temperatures by each participant for the Re-C cell. Uncertainty bars are expanded uncertainties ($k = 2$). (Online version in colour.)

- Introduction
- Radiation thermometry, general introductory theory and practice
- The mise-en-pratique of the kelvin at high temperature
- Realisation of the international temperature scale of 1990
- Thermodynamic temperature (radiance method)
- HTFPs and assigned thermodynamic temperatures
- Dissemination of thermodynamic temperature
- **Conclusion**

- ITS-90 scheme will continue to be used either with T90 reference or T reference as a starting point (with the best uncertainties)
- Uncertainties for direct T measurement limited by the complexity of the methods and stability of the instruments – but yet the most competitive!
- HTFPs have reached a good level of maturity to be T references. 7 points have assigned T values Fe-C, Co-C, Pd-C, Pt-C, Ru-C, Re-C and WC-C
 - Dissemination with HTFPs needs care...

- Quality of the cells (filling rate) is essential

THERMAL EFFECTS: WORK IN PROGRESS...

- Thermal (furnace) effects are still major uncertainty components and ill-understood

COMPARISON OF THE THREE MeP METHODS (LNE-C_{NAM} CASE)

ITS-90

Fixed point	T / K	u_{T90} / mK
Cu	1357,77	/
Co-C	1597,3	70
Pt-C	2011,2	110
Re-C	2747,4	210

- **Pros:** well known, best uncertainties possibly
- **Cons:** not T, depends on instrument characteristics

Direct T

Point fixe	T / K	u_T / mK
Cu	1357,86	68
Co-C	1597,4	96
Pt-C	2011,4	150
Re-C	2747,8	280

- **Pros:** can still be improved, robust, no fixed point needed
- **Cons:** time consuming, needs traceability to cryogenic radiometer

Relative T

Point fixe	T / K	u_T / mK
Cu	1357,86	/
Co-C	1597,4	120
Pt-C	2011,4	190
Re-C	2747,8	340

- **Pros:** easy, competitive uncertainties (compared to direct T... usually)
- **Cons:** interpolation, HTFPs still under study, additional uncertainties in-use

Appendix 2. High temperature fixed points: introductory overview

*Liberté
Égalité
Fraternité*

LABORATOIRE
NATIONAL
DE MÉTROLOGIE
ET D'ESSAIS

le cnam

HIGH TEMPERATURE FIXED POINTS INTRODUCTORY OVERVIEW

FRÉDÉRIC BOURSON

LNE-CNAM

- History of HTFPs cells development: the need of reference above the Cu point
- Thermophysical explanation of eutectic melt and solidification: phase diagrams
- Construction of the cells, filling process, causes of breakage
- Cells characterisation
- Usage of HTFPs
- Description of the cell design

1996: recommendation of the CCT to develop high-temperature references with a target uncertainty of 0,1 °C at 2000 °C

The Cu point ($T_{Cu} = 1357,77$ K) is the highest FP of the ITS-90

The Au point ($T_{Au} = 1337,33$ K) was the highest FP of the ITS for 64 years

Several options considered

THE NEED OF REFERENCES ABOVE THE CU POINT /2

Degree of equivalence of lamps in the key comparison CCT K-5 (23 labs)

Conclusion: large differences, instability, fragility

1996 : recommandation of the CCT to develop high temperature references with a target uncertainty of 0,1 °C at 2000 °C

Phase transitions of pure metals

Metal	$t_{90} / ^\circ\text{C}$	$u(t_{90}) / ^\circ\text{C}$
Palladium	1554.8	0.1
Platinum	1768.2	0.4
Rhodium	1963	3
Iridium	2446	6
Molybdenum	2622	4
Tungsten	3414	7

Conclusion: high uncertainty and poor stability
the ingot is contaminated by the crucible

Bedford R.E. et al. "Recommended values of temperature on the ITS-90 for a selected set of secondary reference points" Metrologia 33 133 (1996)

1996 : recommandation of the CCT to develop high temperature references with a target uncertainty of 0,1 °C at 2000 °C

1999 : Article by Y. Yamada / NMIJ (Japan)

Possibility to construct HTFPs based on M-C eutectic transitions

No contamination of the ingot by the crucible !

Metal purity: 5N-6N (min 4N)

Graphite (to mix with the metal) purity available: 6N

Graphite (crucible) purity available: 5N5

Yamada Y, Sakate H, Sakuma F, Ono A. 1999 "Radiometric observation of melting and freezing plateaus for a series of metal-carbon eutectic points in the range 1330 °C to 1950 °C" Metrologia 36, 207–209

First trials: graphite sleeve inserted in the crucible (2001 → 2003)

Inner sleeve in rigid graphite absorbing mechanical strengths caused by the expansion of the ingot

- ✓ Design based on ITS-90 FPs
- ✗ Robustness

Small size (45 mm x 24 mm) compare to ITS-90 cells: poor robustness and furnace temperature gradients

First trials: replacement of the inner sleeve by the C/C sheets (2003 → 2007)

Layers of C/C sheets (1, 2 or 3) to absorb mechanical strengths and improve the temperature distribution along the ingot (NMIJ)

- ✓ Plateau shape: small melting range, longer duration, better repeatability ...
- ✗ Robustness – stability

Current cell design: hybrid design = both C/C sheets and graphite sleeve (2006 → today)

Combination of C/C sheets (2 layers) and a rigid graphite sleeve (LNE-Cnam)

- ✓ Advantages of both 1st and 2nd designs
- ✗ Still some breakages (less and less)

Mains projects devoted (partly) to the development of HTFPs and their characterisation

JRP HiMERT (2002-2005): Novel High temperature Metal-carbon Eutectic fixed points for Radiation Thermometry, radiometry and thermocouples (first developments, robustness)

JRP HiTeMS (2011-2014): High temperature metrology for industrial applications (thermal conditions furnace effect)

JRP InK (2012-2015): Implementing the new kelvin (T assignment Co-C, Pt-C, Re-C, furnace effect)

Real-K (2020-2023): Realising the redefined kelvin (T assignment Fe-C, Pd-C, Ru-C, WC-C furnace effect)

Projects of **CCT-WG5/NCTh** (characterisation, thermal conditions, reproducibility)

- History of HTFPs cells development: the need of reference above the Cu point
- **Thermophysical explanation of eutectic melt and solidification: phase diagrams**
- Construction of the cells, filling process, cause of breakage
- Cells characterisation
- Usage of HTFPs
- Description of the cell design

METAL-CARBON ALLOY – PHASE DIAGRAM /1

Temperature

METAL-CARBON ALLOY – PHASE DIAGRAM /1

The eutectic composition can be prepared from a hypo-eutectic mixture (less carbon than at the eutectic point) or hyper-eutectic mixture (more carbon than at the eutectic point). At a given temperature and C content two phases will coexist: either the metal-carbon liquid mixture appropriate for the temperature along with excess, solid carbon, or the metal-carbon liquid mixture appropriate for the temperature along with excess, solid metal.

But there is a carbon reservoir available.

HYPO-EUTECTIC: as the temperature is raised the mixture eventually reaches the point where pure metal and the eutectic melt coexists. As the temperature increases further there is segregation of C from the crucible into the metal-eutectic composition, which increases its carbon content.

HYPER-EUTECTIC: As the temperature increases the metal-carbon eutectic melts, with solid carbon present. Upon cooling, carbon will solidify on carbon surfaces until the melt reaches its eutectic point. Further cooling leads to freezing of the melt at exactly the eutectic composition.

METAL-CARBON ALLOY – PHASE DIAGRAM /2

Temperature

METAL-CARBON ALLOY – PHASE DIAGRAM /3

General recommendations

- Preparation of the mixture below the eutectic composition
but some trials at hypereutectic composition: Conference paper Y. Yamada and P. Bloembergen *"High-temperature metal-carbon eutectic fixed-point cells with improved robustness"* SICE 2004 Annual Conference
- $T_{setpoint}$ as close as possible to $T_{eutectic}$

Atomic or weight percentage

- History of HTFPs cells development: the need of reference above the Cu point
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Material: Graphite
Forming: Isostatically pressed
Application: Electronic applications

Choice of graphite

Material data of SIGRAFINE® isostatic graphites

Typical properties	Units	Typical values by grade*						
		CZ3/R6300	R6340	R6500	CZ5.2/R6520	CZ5/R6510	R6650	R6710
Average grain size	µm	20	15	10	10	10	7	3
Bulk density	g/cm ³	1.73	1.72	1.77	1.81	1.83	1.84	1.88
Open porosity	Vol. %	14	15	14	12	10	10	10
Coefficient of permeability (ambient temperature)	cm ² /s	0.1	0.25	0.25		0.06	0.02	0.01
Rockwell hardness _{5/100}				70	80	85	95	105
Rockwell hardness _{10/100}		75	80					
Resistivity	µΩm	16	12	14	13	12	14	13
Flexural strength	MPa	40	45	50	55	60	65	85
Compressive strength	MPa	85	90	110	120	130	150	170
Dynamic modulus of elasticity	MPa	10.0 x 10 ³	11.0 x 10 ³	10.5 x 10 ³	11 x 10 ³	11.5 x 10 ³	12.5 x 10 ³	13.5 x 10 ³
Thermal expansion [20 – 200 °C]	K ⁻¹	2.7 x 10 ⁻⁶	3.2 x 10 ⁻⁶	4.2 x 10 ⁻⁶	4.2 x 10 ⁻⁶	4.2 x 10 ⁻⁶	4.1 x 10 ⁻⁶	4.7 x 10 ⁻⁶
Thermal conductivity [20 °C]	Wm ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	70	105	95	100	110	100	110

* Typical average values of different rectangular and round block sizes. The actual individual block values might vary depending on dimension and format.

Source: <https://www.sglcarbon.com/pdf/SGL-TDS-SIGRAFINE-ISO-for-Electronic-Applications-EN.pdf>

Graphite proportion in the mixture

Alloy	Phase transition °C	Density of pure metal (at 20°C) g/cm ³	Eutectic composition % mass C	Recommended proportion of C % mass	Tolerance	Density eutectic / density pure metal
Fe-C	1153	7.9	4.3	3.5	30 %	90 %
Co-C	1324	8.9	2.6	2		
Pd-C	1492	12.0	4.0	3		
Pt-C	1738	21,4	1.2	0.5		
Re-C	2474	20.8	1.3	0.5		

Typically: A Co-C cell of volume 3 cm³ requires 25 g of Co + 0,5 g of C

Mixture preparation

Metal shots +
graphite powder

Metal powder +
graphite powder

Metal cubes +
graphite powder

- ✓ Number of filling steps
- ✗ Homogeneous mixture

- ✓ Homogeneous mixture
- ✗ Number of filling steps

- ✓ Number of filling steps
- ✗ Homogeneous mixture

General requirements

No need to work under pure atmosphere
(glovebox filled of pure argon)

Open box containing:

- Balance (résolution 0,01g)
- Tools to préparer the mixture and cut the C/C sheets

General requirements

No need to clean the graphite parts
(ultrasonic bath or baking)

Impurities: 5 ppm guaranteed (generally 2-3 ppm)

Possible ways to fill a eutectic cell

Successive fillings:

Only a part of the preparation can be poured in the crucible (especially with metal powders). The process is then repeated up to the complete filling

Piston method:

The totality of the M-C preparation can be poured in the crucible on which an additional extension is mounted.

In the liquid phase, the metal stuck at the surface of the extension is pushed inside the cell by a piston. The excess of metal is collected inside the piston,

Successive fillings:

1st cycle

2nd cycle

Etc

1st filling:

Crucible filled with a part of the mixture (powder)

1st filling:

Crucible partly filled (20 %)

2nd filling:

Solid M-C + mixture (powder)

2nd filling:

Crucible partly filled (35 %)

FILLING PROCESS /6

Crucible filled with the totality of the mixture in powder (a bit more than needed)

Cell after melting/freezing cycle

Cell filled

Possible difficulties

T furnace < T_{melt}
sintering (solid state)

More mixture than
required

Powder spread
everywhere

Comparison of methods: advantages, disadvantages

Successive fillings:

- ✓ Safe way to fill cells
- ✓ Homogeneity of the ingot
- ✗ Contamination from the furnace
- ✗ Difficulty to perform the last steps
- ✗ Time consuming: 3 to 15 steps (meaning 3 to 15 days)

Piston method:

- ✓ Filling in 1 or 2 steps
- ✓ Cells completely filled
- ✓ No contamination by the furnace – sample available
- ✓ No need to know in advance the exact amount of metal
- ✗ Difficult to carry out

Thermal expansion

M-C eutectic/peritectic	Co-C	Pd-C	Pt-C	Cr-C	Ru-C	Re-C	WC-C
Thermal expansion of metal /10e ⁻⁶ .K ⁻¹	12	11.8	9	6.5	9.1	6.5	4.5
Thermal expansion of graphite (R6710) /10 ⁻⁶ .K ⁻¹	4.7						
Temp. difference from the ambient to the melt /K	1301	1469	1715	1803	1930	2451	2726
Difference of expansion cavity/ingot /mm	0.26	0.28	0.18	0.04	0.20	0.05	- 0.11

POSSIBLE CAUSES OF BREAKAGE /2

Influence of the graphite thermal expansion at the Co-C HTFP (16 Co-C cells filled)

Graphite	ATJ49	R4340	R4550	R6510	Poco SFG-2	Total
Coefficient of thermal expansion /10 ⁻⁶ /K	2,5	2,9	4,0	5,1	8,1	
Number of cells filled	1	3	5	4	3	16
Number of broken cells during filling	0	2	3	2	3	10
Number of broken cells after implementation	0	1	2	2	—	5

... but the use of graphite with a high thermal expansion coefficient does not guaranty the cell robustness

Consensus: melting slope < +1200 °C/h and freezinf slope < 800 °C/h

First trials at LNE-Cnam (Himert 2003)

POSSIBLE CAUSES OF BREAKAGE /4

Breakage at the middle of the cavity

Breakage at the entrance of the cavity

Breakage at the middle of the cavity

Breakage at the entrance of the cavity

Solution:
Hybrid cell with
movable cavity

Tests with high increasing/decreasing slopes

- Decreasing slope (power 0%) : 450 °C / 15 mn (1800 °C/h)
- Increasing slope (power 100%): 650 °C / 3 mn (13000 °C/h)

General recommendations

- Proportion of graphite in the mixture below the eutectic composition
- Hybrid design
- Graphite grade: the higher density and small grain size, the better
- Purity of the metal > 4N (99.99 %)
- Purity of the graphite crucible: > 4N5 ppm for the items in contact with the metal)
- Use of glooves when handling the crucibles

- History of HTFPs cells development: the need of reference above the Cu point
- Thermophysical explanation of eutectic melt and solidification: phase diagrams
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- **Cells characterisation**
- Usage of HTFPs
- Description of the cell design

Overview of a melting/freezing cycle (Co-C)

Overview of a melting/freezing cycle (Co-C)

CELLS CHARACTERISATION /3

CELLS CHARACTERISATION /4

High temperature furnaces (1-zone)

3-zone furnace

$T < 1600\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$

$1000\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} < T < 3000\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$

No possibility (or difficult) to adjust the temperature distribution

Possibility to adjust the temperature distribution

The flatter, the better

Resistivity of the pyrolytic graphite rings of HTBB 3200 pg

Ring repositioning vs resistivity

Caractérisation des conditions thermiques du four HTBB 3200 pg à haute température

- $\vec{\nabla}T < 3 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C} / 40 \text{ mm}$
- Position validated by the melting temperature and by the melting range

No possibility to adjust the temperature distribution

The temperature distribution can be characterised

The temperature distribution cannot be characterised

- Movable target + radiation thermometer
- Tilted radiation thermometer (no longer used)

- The cell is positioned close to the expected zone of flat temperature distribution and moved around this position

The quality of the plateaus should confirm that the cell is located in the flattest temperature gradient. This means:

- Lowest melting range
- Best plateau shape
- Highest temperature at the inflexion point (to be linked to the plateau shape)

Furnace effect: melting temperature of a cell implemented in known temperature gradients

CELLS CHARACTERISATION /8

Furnace effect: melting temperature of a cell implemented in known temperature gradients

Cell position / mm

Pyrometer
field of view

Field of view diameter: 1mm

Field of view diameter: 2.5 mm

$$\epsilon_{cavity} \cong 0.9997$$

$$\epsilon_{graphite} \cong 0.86$$

86 % of the flux comes from the cavity bottom
(not sensitive to the furnace TD)

14 % of the flux comes from the cavity wall
(very sensitive to the TD)

Temperature difference measured at the inflexion points as a function of the temperature gradient

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USAGE OF HTFPs /1

Possible eutectic and peritectic fixed points

- Gris : Non renseigné

3 (IIIb)	4 (IVb)	5 (Vb)	6 (VIb)	7 (VIIb)	8 (VIIIb)	9 (VIIIb)	10 (VIIIb)	11 (Ib)
21 Sc Scandium	22 Ti Titane	23 V Vanadium	24 Cr Chrome	25 Mn Manganèse	26 Fe Fer	27 Co Cobalt	28 Ni Nickel	29 Cu Cuivre
39 Y Yttrium	40 Zr Zirconium	41 Nb Niobium	42 Mo Molybdène	43 Tc Technétium	44 Ru Ruthénium	45 Rh Rhodium	46 Pd Palladium	47 Ag Argent
57 La Lanthane	72 Hf Hafnium	73 Ta Tantale	74 W Tungstène	75 Re Rhénium	76 Os Osmium	77 Ir Iridium	78 Pt Platine	79 Au Or

3030 K à 3450 K

Poor reproducibility

Poor robustness

General recommendations

- Temperature distribution along the crucible as flat as possible
- Control of the melting setpoint (max: $T_{melt} + 40$ °C)
- Control of the freezing setpoint (Fe-C and Co-C)
- Heating rate < 1200 °C/h
- Cooling rate < 1000 °C/h to reduce the mechanical stress (especially close to room temperature)

USAGE OF HTFPs: M_EP-K AND DISSEMINATION

Assigned thermodynamic temperatures (lnK - Real-K)

$T_{Cu} = 1358\text{ K}$
 $T_{Fe-C} = 1426\text{ K}$
 $T_{Co-C} = 1597\text{ K}$
 $T_{Pd-C} = 1765\text{ K}$
 $T_{Pt-C} = 2011\text{ K}$
 $T_{Ru-C} = 2226\text{ K}$
 $T_{Re-C} = 2747\text{ K}$
 $T_{WC-C} = 3021\text{ K}$

Thermal conditions
Furnace effect (HiTeMS CCT-WG5/NCTh)

Robustness (Himert, lnK, CCT-WG5/NCTh)

Mignature cells characterised in T by direct comparison to the references

Radiation thermometry below the Ag point (lnK 2)

Dissemination - direct traceability to T or T_{90}

Fixed points for thermocouples calibration (link with the contact thermometry)

ITS-90 fixed points

- History of HTFPs cells development: the need of reference above the Cu point
- Thermophysical explanation of eutectic melt and solidification: phase diagrams
- Construction of the cells, filling process, cause of breakage
- Cells characterisation
- Usage of HTFPs
- **Description of the cell design**

MATERIAL /1

Cell design: crucible and cavity

MATERIAL /2

Cell design: sleeve, ring and extension

Not for ITS-90 cells

MATERIAL /3

Cell design: piston, stopper and cap

Good luck with the cell construction!

Appendix 3. Workshop on interpolation schemes

WORKSHOP ON INTERPOLATION SCHEMES

EPM MultiFixRad

Date: 14th of June 2023

- **MeP-K**
 - **Measured Signal by the Pyrometer: S**
 - The Limiting Effective Wavelength
 - The Reference Wavelength
 - Interpolation Equations for Radiation Thermometry
 - **ITS-90**
 - a) ITS-90 Newton-Raphson Iteration
 - b) ITS-90 Uncertainty
 - **Calibration Schemes**
 - One Fixed-Point Interpolation Scheme ($n=1$)
 - Uncertainty One Fixed-Point Interpolation Scheme ($n=1$)
 - Two Fixed-Point Interpolation Scheme ($n=2$)
 - Uncertainty Two Fixed-Point Interpolation Scheme ($n=2$)
 - Three Fixed-Point Interpolation Scheme ($n=3$)
 - Uncertainty Three Fixed-Point Interpolation Scheme ($n=3$)
 - Comparison of $n = 1$, $n = 2$, and $n = 3$ Methods
 - More than three Fixed-Point Interpolation Scheme ($n>3$)
 - Uncertainty more than three Fixed-Point Interpolation Scheme ($n>3$)
 - Additional Uncertainty Components
- Determination of Optimum Position
 - **Melting Temperatures and Uncertainties of Fixed-Points**
 - **Determination of POI**
 - a) POI Determination CCT-WG5-WP2 Method
 - b) POI Determination Half-width Third-order Polynomial Fitting Method
 - c) POI Determination Selective Multiple Fit Method
 - **Determination of Liquidus and Melting Range**
 - a) Liquidus Point Determination Fraction Method
 - b) Liquidus Point Determination Cross Section Method
 - c) Melting Range Determination
 - **MultiFIX Calculator**
 - a) Adding a New Fixed Point
 - b) Loading Fixed Points Data
 - c) Loading Spectral Sensivity Data
 - d) Modifying Uncertainty Components
 - e) Making a Calibration
 - f) Analyzing the Uncertainty Values of Different Temperatures
 - g) Exporting Data

To realise the kelvin by means of multiple fixed point technique in radiation thermometry

Planck Equation:

$$L_{\lambda}(\lambda) = \frac{c_1}{\lambda^5} \frac{1}{\exp\left(\frac{c_2}{\lambda T_N}\right) - 1}$$

About 15 potential fixed points

Babita, Pant, U., Shivagan, D.D. (2023). Quantum Definition of New Kelvin and Way Forward. In: Aswal, D.K., Yadav, S., Takatsuji, T., Rachakonda, P., Kumar, H. (eds) Handbook of Metrology and Applications. Springer, Singapore.

https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-1550-5_14-1

Measuring the Thermal Radiation Emitted by a Blackbody

Absolute total radiometry and absolute spectral-band radiometry are the two main radiometric techniques that, at least in theory, are suitable at temperatures above the silver point.

Absolute Total Radiometry: Total radiometry gets its name from the fact that it aims to precisely measure the total power (determined by the Stefan-Boltzmann law) emitted by a blackbody with a constant and uniform temperature.

Total radiant exitance

$$M(T) = 2 * \frac{\pi^5 k^4}{15 h^3 c^2} T^4 = \sigma T^4$$

The lowest uncertainty implementation of the method is through the use of a cryogenic electrical substitution radiometer (shown in figure).

Absolute Spectral-band Radiometry

Schematic diagram of the geometry used for measuring the thermal radiation emitted by a blackbody with a filter radiometer. Two apertures of area A_1 and A_2 separated by a distance d define the geometric factor G .

$$I_{photo} = \varepsilon \cdot G \cdot \int s_{E,FR}(\lambda) \cdot L_{\lambda}(\lambda, T) d\lambda$$

- ε : Emissivity of the blackbody
- $s_{E,FR}(\lambda)$: Absolute spectral irradiance responsivity of the filter radiometer

Geometric Factor is given by;

$$G = \frac{2\pi r_1^2}{r_1^2 + r_2^2 + d^2 + \sqrt{(r_1^2 + r_2^2 + d^2)^2 - 4r_1^2 r_2^2}}$$

r_1 and r_2 : radii of the two apertures of areas A_1 and A_2

Absolute Spectral-band Radiometry – Four Different Approaches

Schematic diagram of the differences between calibration and use for the four radiometric methods.

- **The Power Method:** The radiometer is calibrated for spectral power responsivity against a trap detector, using a monochromatic source that underfills the radiometer.
- **The Irradiance Method:** A filter radiometer is calibrated for irradiance responsivity and used with a second aperture added in front of the blackbody for measurement.
- **The Hybrid Method:** A lens is introduced to enable the measurement of smaller radiance sources than the irradiance method. The calibration of the lens transmission and the spectral irradiance responsivity of the filter radiometer are done separately.
- **The Radiance Method:** The radiance of the blackbody is measured using an image radiometer that is calibrated for radiance responsiveness and consists of a filter radiometer integrated into an optical system made up of numerous lenses and suitable baffling.

Measured Signal by the Pyrometer: S

$$S = \int_0^{\infty} N_{\lambda}(\lambda) s(\lambda) d\lambda \quad (1)$$

$N_{\lambda}(\lambda)$: Spectral Radiance

$s(\lambda)$: Sensitivity Function

The Effective Wavelength: λ_e

*This idea was first proposed in 1915.**

$$\frac{M_{\lambda}(\lambda_e)}{N_{\lambda}(\lambda_e)} = \frac{\int_0^{\infty} M_{\lambda}(\lambda) s(\lambda) d\lambda}{\int_0^{\infty} N_{\lambda}(\lambda) s(\lambda) d\lambda} = \frac{S_M}{S_N} \quad (2)$$

The ratio of radiations in a effective wavelength is equal to the ratio of signals. The above equation can be written using Planck's equation as;

$$\frac{M_{\lambda}(\lambda_e)}{N_{\lambda}(\lambda_e)} = \frac{\exp(c_2/\lambda_e T_N) - 1}{\exp(c_2/\lambda_e T_M) - 1} \quad (3)$$

λ_e can be calculated with two different known fixed points.

**Hyde, E. P., Cady, F. E., & Forsythe, W. E. (1915). The Effective Wave-Length of Transmission of Red Pyrometer Glasses and Other Notes on Optical Pyrometry. The Astrophysical Journal, 42, 294.*

Bezemer, J. (1974). Spectral sensitivity corrections for optical standard pyrometers. Metrologia, 10(2), 47.

$$\text{Planck Equation: } N_{\lambda}(\lambda) = \frac{c_1}{\lambda^5} \frac{1}{\exp\left(\frac{c_2}{\lambda T_N}\right) - 1}$$

The Limiting Effective Wavelength

However, by defining the limiting effective wavelength, we can find the effective wavelength with less computation.

$$\lambda_l(T) = \lim_{T_2 \rightarrow T_1 = T} \lambda_e(T_1, T_2)$$

$\lambda_l(T)$: Limiting effective wavelength. **How to calculate?**

➤ We apply the Wien approximation to the Planck equation.

Planck Equation:

$$N_\lambda(\lambda) = \frac{c_1}{\lambda^5} \frac{1}{\exp\left(\frac{c_2}{\lambda T_N}\right) - 1}$$

$$N_\lambda(\lambda, T) = \frac{c_1}{\lambda^5} \frac{1}{\exp\left(\frac{c_2}{\lambda T_N}\right)}$$

Ratio of to measured signal;

$$\frac{M_\lambda(\lambda_e)}{N_\lambda(\lambda_e)} = \frac{S_M}{S_N} = \frac{\exp\left(\frac{c_2}{\lambda_e T_2}\right)}{\exp\left(\frac{c_2}{\lambda_e T_1}\right)}$$

$$\ln\left(\frac{S_1}{S_2}\right) = -\frac{c_2}{\lambda_e} \left(\frac{1}{T_1} - \frac{1}{T_2}\right)$$

$$\lambda_e(\ln S_1 - \ln S_2) = -c_2(1/T_1 - 1/T_2)$$

$$\lambda_e = \frac{-c_2(1/T_1 - 1/T_2)}{\ln S_1 - \ln S_2}$$

By the limiting definition;

$$\lim_{x_2 - x_1 \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(x_1) - f(x_2)}{x_2 - x_1} = \frac{df(x)}{dx}$$

$$\lim_{T_2 \rightarrow T_1 = T} (\lambda_e) = \frac{-c_2(1/T_1 - 1/T_2)}{\ln S_1 - \ln S_2}$$

$$\lambda_l = -c_2 \frac{d(1/T)}{d \ln S} = -c_2 S \frac{d(1/T)}{dS}$$

The Limiting Effective Wavelength

$$S = \int_0^{\infty} N(\lambda, T_N) \delta(\lambda) d\lambda \quad \text{a)}$$

applying the Wien approximation to equation a) ;

$$S = \int_0^{\infty} c_1 \lambda^{-5} \exp\left(-\frac{c_2}{\lambda T_N}\right) \delta(\lambda) d\lambda \quad \text{b)}$$

$$\lambda_1 = -c_2 \frac{d(1/T)}{d \ln S} = -c_2 S \frac{d(1/T)}{dS} \quad \text{c)}$$

Substituting the S term obtained in equation b into equation c ;

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_l} = \frac{-c_2 \int_0^{\infty} \frac{1}{\lambda} N(\lambda) \delta(\lambda) d\lambda}{-c_2 \int_0^{\infty} N(\lambda) \delta(\lambda) d\lambda} \quad \text{d)}$$

Also by integrating equation c ;

$$\int_{T=T_1}^{T_2} \frac{1}{\lambda_1} d\left(\frac{1}{T}\right) = \frac{-1}{c_2} (\ln S_2 - \ln S_1) \quad \text{e)}$$

$$\lambda_e (\ln S_1 - \ln S_2) = -c_2 (1/T_1 - 1/T_2) \quad \text{f)}$$

We will find the relationship between the limiting wavelength and the effective wavelength.

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_e} = \frac{1}{\left(\frac{1}{T_2} - \frac{1}{T_1}\right)} \int_{T=T_1}^{T_2} \frac{1}{\lambda_1} d\left(\frac{1}{T}\right) \quad \text{g)}$$

Generally;

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_l} = \frac{\int_0^{\infty} \frac{1}{\lambda} N(\lambda) \delta(\lambda) d\lambda}{\int_0^{\infty} N(\lambda) \delta(\lambda) d\lambda} \quad \text{h)}$$

according to this equation $\frac{1}{\lambda_1}$; It is a good linear approximation of $\frac{1}{T}$.

The Limiting Effective Wavelength

So equation g can be written like this;

$$\lambda_e(T_1, T_2) = \frac{1}{2} \lambda_1(T_1) + \frac{1}{2} \lambda_1(T_2) \text{ or}$$

$$\lambda_e(T_1, T_2) = \lambda_1(T_3) \text{ with } 1/T_3 = \frac{1}{2} (1/T_1 + 1/T_2)$$

The Limiting Effective wavelength for the five ranges, the effective wavelengths with respect to the goldpoint for the ranges 0 is indicated with the dotted line

The Reference Wavelength

The spectral radiance $N_\lambda(\lambda_r)$ at λ_r can be state as,

$$RN_\lambda(\lambda_r) = \frac{\int_0^\infty N_\lambda(\lambda) s(\lambda) d\lambda}{\int_0^\infty s(\lambda) d\lambda}$$

R: Radiance Correction Factor

λ_r : Reference Wavelength

Using the the Reference Wavelength, Ratio of two radiance $M_\lambda(\lambda)$ and $N_\lambda(\lambda)$ written as;

$$\frac{M_\lambda(\lambda_r)}{N_\lambda(\lambda_r)} = \frac{\exp(c_2/\lambda_r T_N) - 1}{\exp(c_2/\lambda_r T_M) - 1} = \frac{R_N \int_0^\infty M_\lambda(\lambda) s(\lambda) d\lambda}{R_M \int_0^\infty N_\lambda(\lambda) s(\lambda) d\lambda} = \frac{R_N S_M}{R_M S_N}$$

$$\frac{M(\lambda_e)}{N(\lambda_e)} = \frac{R_M M_\lambda(\lambda_r)}{R_N N_\lambda(\lambda_r)}$$

Solving this equation for unknown temperature T_N , we get

$$\frac{1}{T_N} = \frac{\lambda_r}{c_2} \ln \left[\left(\exp(c_2/\lambda_r T_M) - 1 \right) \frac{R_N S_M}{R_M S_N} + 1 \right]$$

This can be easily approximated to

$$\frac{1}{T_N} \cong \frac{1}{T_M} + \frac{\lambda_r}{c_2} \ln \frac{S_M}{S_N} + \frac{\lambda_r}{c_2} (R_N - 1) - \frac{\lambda_r}{c_2} (R_M - 1)$$

$$\Delta \left(\frac{1}{T_N} \right) \cong \frac{\lambda_r}{c_2} (R_N - 1)$$

The difference between the measured value and the real value.

Correction factor R for Planck radiators for the 654 nm interference filter at the range 0 with several reference wavelengths

According to the definition of the ITS-90, the temperature $T_{90} (> 961.78 \text{ °C})$ is defined by the equation,

$$\frac{L_{\lambda}(T_{90})}{L_{\lambda}(T_{90}(X))} = \frac{\exp\left(\frac{c_2}{\lambda T_{90}(X)}\right) - 1}{\exp\left(\frac{c_2}{\lambda T_{90}}\right) - 1}$$

$$L_{\lambda}(T_{90}) = \frac{c_1}{n_{\lambda}^2 \lambda^5} \left[\exp\left(\frac{c_2}{n_{\lambda} \lambda T_{90}}\right) - 1 \right]^{-1}$$

Planck blackbody radiance law

Note:

From here on we drop n_{λ} because we replaced vacuum λ to air λ

The temperature of a blackbody is determined using radiation thermometry by solving the integral equation

$$S = \int_0^{\infty} R(\lambda) L_b(\lambda, T) d\lambda$$

in practice, because radiation thermometers necessarily have a finite spectral bandwidth, and because true blackbodies do not exist and measurements are not made in a vacuum, the monochromatic blackbody spectral radiance ratio given by Equation (1) cannot be measured directly. Instead, the ratio of spectral radiations integrated over the spectral sensitivity of the radiation thermometer, r , should be used to realise $T_{90}(X)$.

$$r = \frac{S(T_{90})}{S_{T_{90}(X)}} = \frac{\int_0^{\infty} \varepsilon(\lambda, T_{90}) L_{\lambda}(T_{90}) R(\lambda) d\lambda}{\int_0^{\infty} \varepsilon_X(\lambda, T_{90}(X)) L_{\lambda}(T_{90}(X)) R(\lambda) d\lambda}$$

ITS-90 are determined by forming the ratio (r) at the unknown temperature and at the defined temperature of either the silver, gold, or copper fixed point, thus requiring knowledge of the relative spectral responsivity, $s(\lambda)$, only.

ITS-90 Newton-Raphson Iteration

Rewriting the equation r in terms of relative spectral responsivity,

$$r' = \frac{S'_{ref}(T_{90})}{S'_x(T_{90}(X))} = \frac{\int_0^{\infty} L_{\lambda}(T_{90})s(\lambda)d\lambda}{\int_0^{\infty} L_{\lambda}(T_{90}(X))s(\lambda)d\lambda}$$

$$I_X = \int_0^{\infty} L_{\lambda}(T_{90}(X))s(\lambda)d\lambda$$

$$T_{90,i+1} = T_{90,i} + \frac{I_x r' - \int_0^{\infty} L_{\lambda}(T_{90,i})s(\lambda)d\lambda}{\frac{c_2}{T_{90,i}^2} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{L_{\lambda}(T_{90,i})s(\lambda)}{\lambda \left[1 - \exp\left(-\frac{c_2}{\lambda T_{90,i}}\right) \right]} d\lambda}$$

If $T_{90,0}$ is chosen to be, say, 2250 K, then equation (11) converges to within 0.1 mK of T_{90} in fewer than 10 iterations for any value of T_{90} between the silver point and 3300 K [Saunders 2003].

?

We Could retrieve the Signal by using ratios.

$$S_x = S_{ref} * \frac{S'_x}{S'_{ref}}$$

$$S'_{ref} = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{s(\lambda)}{\lambda^5 \exp\left(\frac{c2}{\lambda * T_{90}}\right)} d\lambda$$

$$S'_x = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{s(\lambda)}{\lambda^5 \exp\left(\frac{c2}{\lambda * T_{90}(X)}\right)} d\lambda$$

By linearizing the curve and fitting we get coefficient we need for the extrapolation.

$$\text{polyfit}(\ln(S_x), \frac{1}{T_x}, 5)$$

Error of the extrapolation according to ITS90

ITS-90 Uncertainty

$$T_x = \left[(T_{ref} + \delta_{impurity} + \delta_{tempdrop} + \delta_{plateau})^{-1} + \frac{(\lambda + \delta_{wave1} + \delta_{refdet} + \delta_{scattering} + \delta_{drift} + \delta_{side-band})}{C_2} \ln \left(\frac{S_{ref} + \delta_{emis} + \delta_{SSE} + \delta_{linearity} + \delta_{stability} + \delta_{amb} + \delta_{gain}}{S_x} \right) \right]^{-1}$$

Uncertainty Components				Partial Uncertainties				Sensitivity Coefficients			Partial Variance			
Definition	Symbol	Expected value	Unit	Symbol	Value	Unit	Distr. Type	factor	Symbol	Value	Unit	Value	Unit	
Reference temperature	T_{ref}	1357.77	K	u_{Tref}	0.019	K	normal	1		1.10471	unitless	0.00046	K ²	
Impurity effect				$u_{impurity}$	0.012	K	normal	1	$\left(\frac{T_x}{T_{ref}}\right)^2 =$	1.10471		0.013	K	
Temperature drop				$u_{\delta_{temp.drop}}$	0.005	K	rectangular	0.57735		1.10471		0.003	K	
Plateau determination				$u_{\delta_{plateau}}$	0.013	K	normal	1		1.10471		0.014	K	
Repeatability				$u_{\delta_{repeatability}}$	0.008	K	normal	1		1.10471		0.009	K	
Wavelength	λ	6.50E-07	m	$u_{\delta_{wave1}}$	4.05E-10	m	rectangular	0.57735		1.1E+08	K m ⁻¹	6.9E-04	K ²	
Wavelength and bandw				$u_{\delta_{wave.}}$	5.00E-11	m	rectangular	0.57735	$(T_x - T_{ref}) \frac{T_x}{\lambda T_{ref}} =$	1.1E+08		0.003	K	
Reference detector				$u_{\delta_{ref.det.}}$	1.80E-13	m	rectangular	0.57735		1.1E+08		0.000	K	
Scattering and polariza				$u_{\delta_{scattering}}$	9.00E-13	m	rectangular	0.57735	$(T_x - T_{ref}) \frac{T_x}{\lambda T_{ref}} =$	1.1E+08		0.000	K	
Repeatability				$u_{\delta_{repeatability}}$	2.00E-11	m	normal	1		1.1E+08		0.002	K	
Drift				$u_{\delta_{drift}}$	4.00E-10	m	rectangular	0.57735		1.1E+08		0.026	K	
Side-band responsivity				$u_{\delta_{side-band}}$	1.50E-11	m	rectangular	0.57735		1.1E+08		0.001	K	
Constant	C_2	0.014388	m.K	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Determination of signal ratio	S_{ref}/S_x	4.53E-01		$u_{\delta_{ratio}}$	1.05E-03	unitless	rectangular	0.57735	$\frac{\lambda T_x^2}{C_2} =$	92.0055	K	3.11E-03	K ²	
Emissivity				$u_{\delta_{emis}}$	5.00E-04	unitless	normal	1		92.0055		0.046	K	
Size-of-Source Effect				$u_{\delta_{SSE}}$	5.00E-04	unitless	rectangular	0.57735		92.0055		0.027	K	
Nonlinearity				$u_{\delta_{linearity}}$	1.00E-04	unitless	normal	1		92.0055		0.009	K	
Drift / Long term Stability				$u_{\delta_{stability}}$	2.00E-04	unitless	rectangular	0.57735		92.0055		0.011	K	
Amb. Conditions				$u_{\delta_{amb}}$	2.00E-05	unitless	rectangular	0.57735		92.0055		0.001	K	
Amplifier gain				$u_{\delta_{gain}}$	1.00E-04	unitless	rectangular	0.57735		92.0055		0.005	K	
Repeatability				$u_{\delta_{repeatability}}$	1.50E-04	unitless	rectangular	0.57735		92.0055		0.008	K	
Integration					0.0001	K	rectangular	0.57735		1	unitless		0.0000	K ²

Measured temperature	t_x	1153.937	°C						TOTAL VARIANCE	$u_{T_x}^2 =$	4.3E-03	K ²
	T_x	1427.087	K						Standard Uncertainty	$u_{T_x} =$	0.065	K
									Expanded Uncertainty	$U_{T_x} =$	0.131	K
Certificate Value	$T_x = (1427.087 \pm 0.131) K$											
	$T_x = 1427.087 K \quad U = 131 mK \quad k=2$											
									Relative Uncertainty	$U_{T_xrel} =$	9.1E-05	-
									Stated Value	$U_{T_x} =$	131	mK

Interpolation Equations for Radiation Thermometry

$$\text{Sakuma-Hattori Eq. } S = a_1 \exp\left(\frac{-c_2}{a_2 T + a_3}\right)$$

An empirical interpolation equation ; *

$$S = a_1 \exp\left(\frac{-c_2}{\lambda_x T}\right)$$

λ_x : Extended effective wavelength (closely related to limiting wavelength)

**

a_1 : Adjustable Parameter of interpolation equation

$$a_1 = c_1 \int_0^{\infty} \frac{R(\lambda)}{\lambda^5} d\lambda$$

When the limiting effective wavelength has the functional form;

$$\lambda_l = A + \frac{B}{T}$$

(A and B are constants) then the interpolation equation becomes;

The Sakuma-Hattori equation can be generalized as;

**Bezemer, J. (1974). Spectral sensitivity corrections for optical standard pyrometers. *Metrologia*, 10(2), 47.

*Saunders, P. (1997). General interpolation equations for the calibration of radiation thermometers. *Metrologia*, 34(3), 201.

Saunders, P., & White, D. R. (2003). Physical basis of interpolation equations for radiation thermometry. *Metrologia*, 40(4), 195.

Interpolation Equations for Radiation Thermometry

$$S = \int_0^{\infty} R(\lambda)L_b(\lambda, T) d\lambda$$

$L_b(\lambda, T)$: Planck Function at wavelength λ and temperature T ,
 $R(\lambda)$: The absolute spectral responsivity of the thermometer

Lets apply Taylor Expansion to the Planck Radiation equation around mean wavelength of λ_0 ;

$$L_b(\lambda, T) = L_b(\lambda_0, T) + (\lambda - \lambda_0) \left(\frac{\partial L_b(\lambda, T)}{\partial \lambda} \right) \Big|_{\lambda = \lambda_0} + \frac{(\lambda - \lambda_0)^2}{2!} \left(\frac{\partial^2 L_b(\lambda, T)}{\partial \lambda^2} \right) \Big|_{\lambda = \lambda_0} + \frac{(\lambda - \lambda_0)^3}{3!} \left(\frac{\partial^3 L_b(\lambda, T)}{\partial \lambda^3} \right) \Big|_{\lambda = \lambda_0} + \dots$$

The mean wavelength is given by,

$$\lambda_0 = \frac{\int_0^{\infty} \lambda R(\lambda) d\lambda}{\int_0^{\infty} R(\lambda) d\lambda}$$

If the Taylor expansion is substituted into the measured signal equation and **the Wien approximation** is applied, it can be arranged as follows:

$$S(T) = \left(\int_0^{\infty} R(\lambda) d\lambda \right) \frac{c_1}{\lambda_0^5} \left(\frac{-c_2}{\lambda_0 T} \right) \times \left[\left(1 + \frac{15\mu_2}{\lambda_0^2} - \frac{35\mu_3}{\lambda_0^3} + \frac{70\mu_4}{\lambda_0^4} \dots \right) - \left(\frac{6\mu_2}{\lambda_0^2} - \frac{21\mu_3}{\lambda_0^3} + \frac{56\mu_4}{\lambda_0^4} \dots \right) \left(\frac{c_2}{\lambda_0 T} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\mu_2}{\lambda_0^2} - \frac{7\mu_3}{\lambda_0^3} + \frac{28\mu_4}{\lambda_0^4} \dots \right) \left(\frac{c_2}{\lambda_0 T} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{6} \left(\frac{\mu_3}{\lambda_0^3} - \frac{8\mu_4}{\lambda_0^4} \dots \right) \left(\frac{c_2}{\lambda_0 T} \right)^3 + \frac{1}{24} \left(\frac{\mu_4}{\lambda_0^4} \dots \right) \left(\frac{c_2}{\lambda_0 T} \right)^4 + \dots \right]$$

μ_i are the central moments of the spectral responsivity

$$\mu_i = \frac{\int_0^{\infty} (\lambda - \lambda_0)^i R(\lambda) d\lambda}{\int_0^{\infty} R(\lambda) d\lambda}$$

$$\mu_1 = 0 \quad \mu_2 = \sigma^2$$

Interpolation Equations for Radiation Thermometry

If we expand Sakuma-Hattori eq. Extended Generalized Sakuma-Hattori equation the parameters a_2, a_3, a_4 related to $\lambda_0, \mu_2, \mu_3, \mu_4, \dots$

$$a_2 = \lambda_0 \left[1 - 6 \frac{\mu_2}{\lambda_0^2} + 21 \frac{\mu_3}{\lambda_0^3} - 14 \frac{(4\mu_4 - 9\mu_2^2)}{\lambda_0^4} + \dots \right]$$

$$a_3 = \frac{c_2}{2} \left[\frac{\mu_2}{\lambda_0^2} - 7 \frac{\mu_3}{\lambda_0^3} + 7 \frac{(4\mu_4 - 9\mu_2^2)}{\lambda_0^4} + \dots \right]$$

$$a_4 = \frac{c_2^2}{6\lambda_0} \left[\frac{\mu_3}{\lambda_0^3} - \frac{1(16\mu_4 - 39\mu_2^2)}{2\lambda_0^4} + \dots \right]$$

For narrow bandwidths, only terms up to μ_2 may be included. Thus the coefficients can be approximated to;

$$a_2 = \lambda_0 \left[1 - 6 \left(\frac{\sigma}{\lambda_0} \right)^2 \right]$$

$$a_3 = \frac{c_2^2}{2} \left(\frac{\sigma}{\lambda_0} \right)^2$$

$$a_4 = 0$$

Planck Equations:

The Planck version of Interpolation Function can be given by;

$$S = \frac{a_1}{\exp(c_2/\lambda_x T) - 1}$$

Planck's law can be written as a geometric series of Wien equations,

$$\frac{c_1}{\lambda^5} \left[\exp\left(\frac{c_2}{\lambda T}\right) - 1 \right]^{-1} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{c_1}{\lambda^5} \exp\left(\frac{-c_2 n}{\lambda T}\right)$$

Using this equation for sufficiently the narrow bandwidth(satisfying the condition $\frac{c_2 \sigma^2}{2\lambda_0^3} \ll 1$) the Planck version of generalized Sakuma-Hattori eq. Can be written as;

$$S = \frac{a_1}{\exp[c_2/(a_2 T + a_3 + a_4/T + a_5/T^2 \dots)] - 1}$$

$$S = \frac{a_1}{\exp \left[c_2 \frac{\left(a_2 + \frac{a_3}{T} + \frac{a_4}{T^2} + \dots \right)}{T} \right] - 1}$$

Coefficients of the Planck version of generalized Sakuma-Hattori equation are not change.

Note:

$$a_2 = \lambda_0 \left[1 - 6 \frac{\mu_2}{\lambda_0^2} + 21 \frac{\mu_3}{\lambda_0^3} - 14 \frac{(4\mu_4 - 9\mu_2^2)}{\lambda_0^4} + \dots \right]$$

$$a_3 = \frac{c_2}{2} \left[\frac{\mu_2}{\lambda_0^2} - 7 \frac{\mu_3}{\lambda_0^3} + 7 \frac{(4\mu_4 - 9\mu_2^2)}{\lambda_0^4} + \dots \right]$$

$$a_4 = \frac{c_2^2}{6\lambda_0} \left[\frac{\mu_3}{\lambda_0^3} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{(16\mu_4 - 39\mu_2^2)}{\lambda_0^4} + \dots \right]$$

Calibration Schemes

$$S = \int_0^{\infty} N_{\lambda}(\lambda) s(\lambda) d\lambda \quad \lambda_0 = \frac{\int_0^{\infty} \lambda s(\lambda) d\lambda}{\int_0^{\infty} s(\lambda) d\lambda} \quad \sigma^2 = \frac{\int_0^{\infty} (\lambda - \lambda_0)^2 s(\lambda) d\lambda}{\int_0^{\infty} s(\lambda) d\lambda}$$

Below equation can be reduced to much simpler form by assigning new variables

$$S = \frac{a_1}{\exp\left[\frac{c_2}{\lambda_0} \left(1 - 6 \frac{\sigma^2}{\lambda_0^2}\right) T + \frac{c_2 \sigma^2}{2 \lambda_0^2} \right] - 1}$$

$$A = \lambda_0 \left(1 - 6 \frac{\sigma^2}{\lambda_0^2}\right), \quad B = \frac{c_2 \sigma^2}{2 \lambda_0^2}, \quad C = Kn^2 \frac{c_1}{\lambda_0} \left(1 + 15 \frac{\sigma^2}{\lambda_0^2}\right) \int_0^{\infty} s(\lambda) d\lambda = \frac{H}{\lambda_0^5} \left(1 + 15 \frac{\sigma^2}{\lambda_0^2}\right)$$

K contains any geometrical and electrical factors not included in the spectral responsivity

$$S = C \exp\left(\frac{-c_2}{AT+B}\right)$$

Interpolation scheme can be found either calculating A , B , C for $n=0$ (absolute radiometry) or by solving the Sakuma-Hattori equation for a_1 , σ and λ_0 by substituting 1, 2, 3 fixed-point

Uncertainty Absolute Radiometric Scheme (n=0)

Each sensitivity coefficients of the model function are found, and corresponding Uncertainties are plotted. **After applying the Wien and zero-bandwidth ($\sigma/\lambda_0 \ll 1$) approximations**, these are:

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial \lambda_0} = \frac{\partial S}{\partial \lambda_0} / \frac{\partial S}{\partial T} \approx \frac{T}{\lambda_0} \left(1 - 5 \frac{\lambda_0 T}{c'_2} \right)$$

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial \sigma} = \frac{\partial S}{\partial \sigma} / \frac{\partial S}{\partial T} \approx \left(\frac{30T^2}{c'_2} - \frac{12T}{\lambda_0} + \frac{c'_2}{\lambda_0^2} \right) \frac{\sigma}{\lambda_0}$$

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial H} = \frac{\partial S}{\partial H} / \frac{\partial S}{\partial T} \approx \frac{\lambda_0 T^2}{c'_2} \frac{1}{H}$$

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial S} = \frac{1}{\partial S / \partial T} \approx \frac{\lambda_0 T^2}{c'_2} \frac{1}{S}$$

$$S = \frac{a_1}{\exp[c_2 / (\lambda_0 (1 - 6\sigma^2 / \lambda_0^2) T + c_2 \sigma^2 / 2\lambda_0^2)] - 1}$$

Model Function

$$S(T) = \frac{C}{\exp\left(\frac{c'_2}{AT + B}\right) - 1}$$

Note:

Although there is an uncertainty component for c'_2 ($\partial T / \partial c'_2 = -T / c'_2$), it is overshadowed by the 0.00017% uncertainty in k , the Boltzmann constant. There is very little ambiguity (5.6 mk at 3000 °C).

$$u_T = \left[\left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial \lambda_0} u_{\lambda_0} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial \sigma} u_{\sigma} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial H} u_H \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial S} u_S \right)^2 \right]^{1/2}$$

One Fixed-Point Interpolation Scheme (n=1)

For narrow bandwidth The relative spectral responsivity can be used to determine both λ_0 and σ , while the fixed point measurement allows a_1 to be determined:

$$S_{ref} = \frac{a_1}{\exp \left[c_2 / \left(\lambda_0 \left(1 - 6\sigma^2 / \lambda_0^2 \right) T_{ref} + c_2 \sigma^2 / 2\lambda_0^2 \right) \right] - 1}$$

$$S = \frac{a_1}{\exp \left[c_2 / \left(\lambda_0 \left(1 - 6\sigma^2 / \lambda_0^2 \right) T + c_2 \sigma^2 / 2\lambda_0^2 \right) \right] - 1}$$

Rectangular Spectral
responsivity

$$\mu_2 = \frac{FWHM^2}{12} = \sigma^2$$

Mean wavelength of
the Relative spectral
responsivity

$$\lambda_0 = \frac{\int_0^\infty \lambda s(\lambda) d\lambda}{\int_0^\infty s(\lambda) d\lambda}$$

$r = \sigma / \lambda_0 = 0.01$. narrow bandwidth

One Fixed-Point Interpolation Scheme (n=1)

a_1 is found from 1 unknown 1 equation

$$a_1 = S_{\text{ref}} * \exp \left[c_2 / \left(\lambda_0 \left(1 - 6\sigma^2 / \lambda_0^2 \right) T_{\text{ref}} + c_2 \sigma^2 / 2\lambda_0^2 \right) \right] - 1$$

Uncertainty One Fixed-Point Interpolation Scheme (n=1)

Each sensitivity coefficients of the model function are found and corresponding Uncertainties are plotted. After applying the Wien and zero-bandwidth approximations, these are:

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial S_{\text{ref}}} = \frac{\partial S}{\partial S_{\text{ref}}} / \frac{\partial S}{\partial T} \approx \frac{\lambda_0 T^2}{c'_2} \frac{1}{S_{\text{ref}}}$$

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial T_{\text{ref}}} = \frac{\partial S}{\partial T_{\text{ref}}} / \frac{\partial S}{\partial T} \approx -\frac{T^2}{T_{\text{ref}}^2}$$

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial \sigma} = \frac{\partial S}{\partial \sigma} / \frac{\partial S}{\partial T} \approx \left(\frac{1}{T_{\text{ref}}} - \frac{1}{T} \right) \left[12 - \frac{c'_2}{\lambda_0} \left(\frac{1}{T_{\text{ref}}} + \frac{1}{T} \right) \right] \frac{T^2 \sigma}{\lambda_0^2}$$

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial \lambda_0} = \frac{\partial S}{\partial \lambda_0} / \frac{\partial S}{\partial T} \approx \frac{T}{\lambda_0} \left(1 - \frac{T}{T_{\text{ref}}} \right)$$

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial S} = \frac{1}{\partial S / \partial T} \approx \frac{\lambda_0 T^2}{c'_2} \frac{1}{S}$$

$$S_{\text{ref}} = C \exp \left(\frac{-c_2}{AT_{\text{ref}} + B} \right)$$

$$S_x = C \exp \left(\frac{-c_2}{AT_x + B} \right)$$

$$u_T = \left[\left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial \lambda_0} u_{\lambda_0} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial \sigma} u_{\sigma} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial T_{\text{ref}}} u_{T_{\text{ref}}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial S_{\text{ref}}} u_{S_{\text{ref}}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial S} u_S \right)^2 \right]^{1/2}$$

Uncertainty One Fixed-Point Interpolation Scheme (n=1, Cu)

Uncertainty Components	Value
λ_0	
Monochromator scale	0.01 nm
Reference detector	0.00018 nm
Scattering, polarization	0.0006 nm
Out-of-band transmittance	0.002 nm
Drift	0.01 nm
Repeatability	0.0018 nm
Total λ_0	0.014 nm
Total σ	0.00014 nm
Total T_{ref} (Cu, 1357.802 K)	80 mK
S_{ref}	
Emissivity of fixed point	0.01 %
Ambient conditions	0.002 %
Repeatability	0.003 %
Total S_{ref}	0.011 %
In-use S	
SSE	0.01%
Non-linearity	0.005 %
Gain ratios	0.01 %
Ambient conditions	0.002 %
Drift	0.01 %
Repeatability	0.003 %
In-use S	0.018 %

This method can also be applied to the ITS-90 by taking total T_{ref} uncertainty component as 0 mk.

Two Fixed-Point Interpolation Scheme (n=2)

$$S_1 = \frac{a_1}{\exp\left[c_2 / (\lambda_0 (1 - 6\sigma^2 / \lambda_0^2) T_1 + c_2 \sigma^2 / 2\lambda_0^2) \right] - 1}$$

$$S_2 = \frac{a_1}{\exp\left[c_2 / (\lambda_0 (1 - 6\sigma^2 / \lambda_0^2) T_2 + c_2 \sigma^2 / 2\lambda_0^2) \right] - 1}$$

$$\sigma = \frac{FWHM}{2\sqrt{3}}$$

a_1 and λ_0 is found by substituting 2 Fixed-Point signal and temperature to the equation and numerically solving.

$$r = \sigma / \lambda_0 = 0.01$$

Two Fixed-Point Interpolation Scheme (n=2)

Each sensitivity coefficients of the model function are found and corresponding Uncertainties are plotted. After applying the Wien and zero-bandwidth approximations, these are:

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial \sigma} \approx -\frac{(T - T_1)(T - T_2)c'_2\sigma}{T_1T_2\lambda_0^3}$$

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial T_1} \approx \frac{T(T - T_2)}{T_1(T_1 - T_2)}$$

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial T_2} \approx \frac{T(T - T_1)}{T_2(T_2 - T_1)}$$

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial S_1} \approx \frac{\lambda_0 T T_1 (T - T_2)}{c'_2 (T_1 - T_2)} \frac{1}{S_1}$$

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial S_2} \approx \frac{\lambda_0 T T_2 (T - T_1)}{c'_2 (T_2 - T_1)} \frac{1}{S_2}$$

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial S} \approx \frac{\lambda_0 T^2}{c'_2} \frac{1}{S}$$

$$S_1 = C \exp\left(\frac{-c_2}{AT_1 + B}\right)$$

$$S_2 = C \exp\left(\frac{-c_2}{AT_2 + B}\right)$$

$$S_x = C \exp\left(\frac{-c_2}{AT_x + B}\right)$$

$$u_T = \left[\left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial \sigma} u_\sigma\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial T_1} u_{T_1}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial T_2} u_{T_2}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial S_1} u_{S_1}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial S_2} u_{S_2}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial S} u_S\right)^2 \right]^{1/2}$$

An extra uncertainty, due to interpolation error, should also be added in quadrature to total uncertainty, but for narrow bandwidths this is negligible.

Uncertainty Two Fixed-Point Interpolation Scheme (n=2)

Uncertainty Components	Value
Total σ	0.00014 nm
Total T1 (Cu, 1357.802 K)	80 mK
Total T2 (Re-C, 2747.84K)	350 mK
S1	
Emissivity of fixed point	0.00 %
Ambient conditions	0.001 %
Repeatability	0.034 %
Total S1	0.034 %
S2	
Emissivity of fixed point	0.00 %
Ambient conditions	0.001 %
SEE	0.01 %
Gain ratio	0.01 %
Repeatability	0.006 %
Total S2	0.015 %
In-use S	
SSE	0.01%
Non-linearity	0.00 %
Gain ratios	0.01 %
Ambient conditions	0.001 %
Drift	0.01 %
Repeatability	0.035 %
In-use S	0.039 %

Three Fixed-Point Interpolation Scheme (n=3)

$$S_1 = \frac{a_1}{\exp\left[c_2 / (\lambda_0 (1 - 6\sigma^2 / \lambda_0^2) T_1 + c_2 \sigma^2 / 2\lambda_0^2) \right] - 1}$$

$$S_2 = \frac{a_1}{\exp\left[c_2 / (\lambda_0 (1 - 6\sigma^2 / \lambda_0^2) T_2 + c_2 \sigma^2 / 2\lambda_0^2) \right] - 1}$$

$$S_3 = \frac{a_1}{\exp\left[c_2 / (\lambda_0 (1 - 6\sigma^2 / \lambda_0^2) T_3 + c_2 \sigma^2 / 2\lambda_0^2) \right] - 1}$$

The three measurements completely specify a_1 , σ and λ_0 . These parameters found by substituting 3 Fixed-Point signal and temperature to the equation and numerically solving.

Although no measurements of the spectral responsivity have been made, the calculated values for λ_0 and σ are very close to the true values.

Three Fixed-Point Interpolation Scheme (n=3)

Each sensitivity coefficients of the model function are found and corresponding Uncertainties are plotted. After applying the Wien and zero-bandwidth approximations, these are:

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial T_1} \approx \frac{(T - T_2)(T - T_3)}{(T_1 - T_2)(T_1 - T_3)}$$

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial T_2} \approx \frac{(T - T_1)(T - T_3)}{(T_2 - T_1)(T_2 - T_3)}$$

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial T_3} \approx \frac{(T - T_1)(T - T_2)}{(T_3 - T_1)(T_3 - T_2)}$$

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial S_1} \approx \frac{\lambda_0 T_1^2}{c'_2} \frac{(T - T_2)(T - T_3)}{(T_1 - T_2)(T_1 - T_3)} \frac{1}{S_1}$$

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial S_2} \approx \frac{\lambda_0 T_2^2}{c'_2} \frac{(T - T_1)(T - T_3)}{(T_2 - T_1)(T_2 - T_3)} \frac{1}{S_2}$$

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial S_3} \approx \frac{\lambda_0 T_3^2}{c'_2} \frac{(T - T_1)(T - T_2)}{(T_3 - T_1)(T_3 - T_2)} \frac{1}{S_3}$$

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial S} \approx \frac{\lambda_0 T^2}{c'_2} \frac{1}{S}$$

$$S_1 = C \exp\left(\frac{-c_2}{AT_1 + B}\right)$$

$$S_2 = C \exp\left(\frac{-c_2}{AT_2 + B}\right)$$

$$S_3 = C \exp\left(\frac{-c_2}{AT_3 + B}\right)$$

$$S_x = C \exp\left(\frac{-c_2}{AT_x + B}\right)$$

$$u_T = \left[\left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial T_1} u_{T_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial T_2} u_{T_2} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial T_3} u_{T_3} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial S_1} u_{S_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial S_2} u_{S_2} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial S_3} u_{S_3} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial S} u_S \right)^2 \right]^{1/2}$$

An extra uncertainty, due to interpolation error, should also be added in quadrature to total uncertainty, but for narrow bandwidths this is negligible.

Uncertainty Three Fixed-Point Interpolation Scheme (n=3)

Uncertainty Components	Value
Total T1 (Cu, 1357.802 K)	80 mK
Total T2 (Co-C, 1597.39K)	110 mK
Total T3 (Re-C, 2747.84K)	350 mK
S1	
Emissivity of fixed point	0.00 %
Ambient conditions	0.001 %
Repeatability	0.009 %
Total S1	0.009 %
S2	
Emissivity of fixed point	0.00 %
Ambient conditions	0.001 %
SEE	0.01 %
Gain ratio	0.01 %
Repeatability	0.006 %
Total S2	0.015 %
S3	
Emissivity of fixed point	0.00 %
Ambient conditions	0.001 %
SEE	0.01 %
Gain ratio	0.01 %
Repeatability	0.003 %
Total S3	0.015 %
In-use S	
SSE	0.02%
Non-linearity	0.015 %
Gain ratios	0.01 %
Ambient conditions	0.001 %
Drift	0.006 %
Repeatability	0.034 %
Alignment of radiometer	0.02 %
In-use S	0.048 %

Saunders, P., & White, D. R. (2003). Physical basis of interpolation equations for radiation thermometry. Metrologia, 40(4), 195.

Uncertainty Three Fixed-Point Interpolation Scheme (n=3)

Uncertainty Components	Value
Total T1 (Cu, 1357.802 K)	80 mK
Total T2 (Co-C, 1597.39K)	110 mK
Total T3 (Re-C, 2747.84K)	350 mK
S1	
Emissivity of fixed point	0.00 %
Ambient conditions	0.001 %
Repeatability	0.009 %
Total S1	0.009 %
S2	
Emissivity of fixed point	0.00 %
Ambient conditions	0.001 %
SEE	0.01 %
Gain ratio	0.01 %
Repeatability	0.006 %
Total S2	0.015 %

S3	
Emissivity of fixed point	0.00 %
Ambient conditions	0.001 %
SEE	0.01 %
Gain ratio	0.01 %
Repeatability	0.003 %
Total S3	0.015 %
In-use S	
SSE	0.02%
Non-linearity	0.015 %
Gain ratios	0.01 %
Ambient conditions	0.001 %
Drift	0.006 %
Repeatability	0.034 %
Alignment of radiometer	0.02 %
In-use S	0.048 %

Comparison of $n = 1$, $n = 2$, and $n = 3$ Methods

The results presented here provide a justification for the use of interpolation equations as a basis for a future ITS above the copper point without sacrificing its close association with the thermodynamic scale.

More than three Fixed-Point Interpolation Scheme (n>3)

Measurements at more than three fixed points allow a least-squares determination of a_1 , λ_0 , and σ in to be made. The redundant points provide a measure of the departure of the exact behaviour of the thermometer from the model equation.

$$S_i = C \exp\left(\frac{-c_2}{AT_i + B}\right)$$

Although there is no overall reduction in the temperature error over the $n = 3$ curve, the propagated uncertainty arising from uncertainties in the measurements decreases as more fixed points are used.

Uncertainty than tree Fixed-Point Interpolation Scheme (n>3)

Since it is tedious job to derive all the sensitivity coefficient by hand it is possible to find sensitivity coefficient the following way:

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial T_n} = \prod_i^N \frac{T - T_i}{T_n - T_i}$$

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial S_n} = \frac{\lambda_0 T_n^2}{c_2 S_n} \prod_i^N \frac{T - T_i}{T_n - T_i}$$

For least-squares fitting the combined uncertainty decreases with the number of measurements used.

Least-Square fitting($n>3$)

Importance of initial guess: For the least square fitting it is important to note that initial guess has to be logical (i.e. Calculated from $n=1$ or 2 or 3) otherwise algorithm can converge to local minima. To solve this, some optimization algorithms can also be used (i.e. randomized maximum likelihood method.)

In our laboratory we use Levenberg–Marquardt Algorithm which uses following minimization function;

$$x = \arg \min(\text{sum}(\text{func}(y)**2))$$

Additional Uncertainty Components

Additional Uncertainty Components

The HTFPs in the MeP-K-19 each have an associated uncertainty in the assigned temperature, which must be combined with the uncertainty of the physical realization of the actual fixed-point cell being evaluated. This is in contrast to the fixed points used in ITS-90, which have zero uncertainty by definition.

Temperature drop, structure effect, identification of the point-of-inflection (POI) or identification of the liquidus point, HTFP stability, impurities, furnace effect, emissivity and uncertainties of unknown origin ('unknown' uncertainties) are among the uncertainty components that need to be taken into account.

Uncertainty Scheme 1

Item	Source	Present best estimates of uncertainty ($k = 1$)/mK					
		Co-C		Pt-C		Re-C	
		Best	Normal	Best	Normal	Best	Normal
Temperature drop		4	9	11	23	48	80
Structure effect		14	14	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Identification of T		24	24	44	44	69	69
Stability		38	38	70	70	31	144
Impurities		8	38	10	37	11	106
Furnace effect		80	80	125	125	240	240
Emissivity		14	14	18	18	25	25
Unknown		16	61	12	69	44	70
Liquidus T		70	70	110	110	220	220
Total		119	138	188	204	342	393

Uncertainty Scheme 2

Item	Source	Present best estimates of uncertainty ($k = 1$)/mK					
		Co-C		Pt-C		Re-C	
		Best	Normal	Best	Normal	Best	Normal
Structure effect		14	14	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Identification of T		3	6	5	6	1	6
Stability		38	38	70	70	31	144
Furnace effect		80	80	125	125	240	240
T (radiometer)		96	221	150	316	280	567
Total		131	239	207	347	370	632

Melting Temperatures and Uncertainties of Fixed-Points

Fixed Points	T, K	U, K	T, °C	U, °C
Cu	1357,80	±0.08	1084,65	±0.08
Co-C	1597,39	±0.13	1324,24	±0.13
Pt-C	2011,13	±0.18	1737,98	±0.18
Fe-C	2777,84	±0.35	2504,69	±0.35

Woolliams, E. R., Anhalt, K., Ballico, M., Bloembergen, P., Bourson, F., Briaudeau, S., ... & Yuan, Z. (2016). Thermodynamic temperature assignment to the point of inflection of the melting curve of high-temperature fixed points. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences*, 374(2064), 20150044.

Melting Temperatures and Uncertainties of Eutectic Cell

Fixed Point	NMI	T, K	U, K	T, °C	U, °C
Fe-C	CNAM	1426,69	0,21	1153,54	0,21
	NPL	1426,76	0,11	1153,61	0,11
	UME	1426,70	0,18	1153,55	0,18
Pd-C	CNAM	1765,06	0,27	1491,91	0,27
	NPL	1764,96	0,21	1491,81	0,21
	UME	1764,95	0,36	1491,80	0,36
Ru-C	CNAM	2227,01	0,39	1953,86	0,39
	NPL	2227,07	0,40	1953,92	0,40
	UME	2226,77	0,50	1953,62	0,50
WC-C	CNAM	3020,94	0,73	2747,79	0,73
	NPL	3021,08	1,03	2747,93	1,03
	UME	3020,45	1,05	2747,30	1,05

Sadli, M. et all. (2023) Realizing the redefined kelvin: thermodynamic temperatures of Fe-C, Pd-C, Ru-C and WC-C for the mise-en-pratique of the kelvin up to 3020 K. Proceeding at ITS-10, USA

Realisation of Eutectic Fixed-Point

Determination of Optimum Position

D1 (26mm):	1 Ring
D2 (12mm):	4 Ring + D1
D3 (8mm):	6 Ring + D2
Cell Holder:	9 Ring + D3
D4 (8mm):	6 Ring + Cell
D5 (8mm):	8 Ring + D4
Back	5 Ring + D5

Determination of POI

POI Determination CCT-WG5-WP2 Method

POI was determined by minimum of first-order differential

Initial Average Lengths	Standard Deviation (K)
5-10-20 Points	0.021662
10-20-40 Points	0.002984
20-40-80 Points	0.002219

This method was proposed by Yamada in CCT-WG5-WP2 for determination of Point of inflection.

Method suggests, smoothing the melting plateau by taking the moving average with a certain initial averaging length. Then the average length was doubled and halved, and the corresponding values of POI were determined.

Determination of POI

POI Determination Half-width Third-order Polynomial Fitting Method

The international project “Implementing the new kelvin” (InK) for the analysis of HTFP melting plateaus used this method which was applied only to the central half of the plateau. Melt start and Melt end points are determined as extremum points of the first derivative.

The POI is determined by applying 3rd order polynomial fit between second and third quartile

Determination of POI

POI Determination Selective Multiple Fit Method

This method uses first- and second-order derivatives of the melting plateau to determine the start and end points but uses an interval between the inner and outer limits as a fitting range for a third-order polynomial fit.

This method uses same mathematical expression as previous method. This procedure produces a large number of fitting results, from which only those satisfying a selection criterion are selected and averaged to obtain the final fitting curve.

Determination of POI

Liquidus Point Determination Fraction Method

Once the start and end points of the melt have been identified, then the fraction melted (F) at any temperature can be found, assuming a constant rate of heat input

The equation $T(F) = T_{liq}F^\alpha$ was fitted to the melting curve up to the fraction at the POI to give T_{liq} . The starting point for the fit was varied to determine the sensitivity to chosen fitted range.

Determination of POI

Liquidus Point Determination Cross Section Method

Liquidus point is an identifiable point on a binary equilibrium phase diagram, with physical significance: it is the temperature above which an alloy of given composition, in thermodynamic equilibrium, is completely liquid.

Here we fitted one linear function to the data near the POI and a second linear function to the data where the derivative after melting had completed was a maximum. Where the two functions intersected was taken to be the “upper limit” of the liquidus temperature.

The equilibrium liquidus temperature is taken to lie somewhere in between POI and upper limit. Since liquidus temperature probability distribution is rectangular mid-point is taken as the Liquidus point.

Determination of POI

Melting Range Determination

Melting range is a common metric for qualification of eutectic fixed-point.

The melting ranges of the eutectic fixed points were evaluated by multiplying the slope of the tangent at the inflection point by the duration of the melting plateau.

MultiFIX v0.0.2_beta

File Options

Run ITS 90

Fixed Points:

Select	Name	Temperature
1	Co-C	1597.39 K
2	Cu	1357.802 K
3	Re-C	2747.84 K
4	Ru-C	2227.1 K
5	WC-C	3020.75 K

Fixed Points

Model Function (Sakuma-Hattori):

$$S = \frac{a_1}{\exp\left(\frac{c_2'}{a_2 T + a_3}\right) - 1}, a_2 = \lambda_0 \left(1 - 6 \frac{\sigma^2}{\lambda_0^2}\right), a_3 = \frac{c_2' \sigma^2}{2 \lambda^2}, c_2' = \frac{hc}{k_b n}$$

Save

Standard Deviation (nm): σ 3.957 nm

Components

Component	Value	Unit
1 Total	0.00014	nm

Save

Mean Wavelength (nm): λ_0 650.570 nm

Components

Component	Value	Unit
1 Monochromator scale	0.01	nm
2 Reference detector	0.00018	nm
3 Scattering, polarisation	0.0006	nm
4 Out-of-band transmittance	0.002	nm
5 Drift	0.01	nm
6 Repeatability	0.0018	nm

Save

In-use Signal: S_{in}

Components

Component	Value	Unit
1 SSE	0.01	%
2 Non-linearity	0.005	%
3 Gain ratios	0.01	%

Graph Table

Sakuma-Hattori Equation Coefficients: a1: 0.0031691951854187776 a2: 6.504251884409335e-07 a3: 2.6617187426251634e-07

Temperature (K): Signal: Calculate

Calibration (Cu)

Temperature, K

Signal, a.u.

Fixed points for calibration

Uncertainty components

Model function (Sakuma -Hattori) for calculation

Calculated Sakuma-Hattori coefficients

Calculated calibration and uncertainty graph

Adding a New Fixed Point

The screenshot shows the MultiFIX v0.0.2 beta interface. The 'File' menu is open, and the 'New' option is highlighted. A red arrow points from the 'New' button to the 'MultiFIX' dialog box. The dialog box contains the following fields and tables:

Name:

Temperature: Signal:

Temperature Uncertainties:

Component	Value	Unit
1 Total	3.5E+03	mK

Signal Uncertainties:

Component	Value	Unit
1 Emissivity of fixed point	0.0	%
2 Ambient conditions	0.001	%
3 SSE	0.01	%
4 Gain ratios	0.01	%
5 Repeatability	0.006	%

Buttons: Add, Close

After pressing the New button, the temperature, signal and uncertainty components related to the fixed point are entered and the Add button is pressed.

MultiFIX Calculator

Loading Fixed Points Data

Click the Load Fixed Point button.

Fixed point data previously saved on the computer is selected.

Fixed points are loaded into the software.

Loading Spectral Sensivity Data

Click the Load Sensor Data button.

Spectral sensitivity data previously saved on the computer is selected.

After the data is loaded, Standard Deviation (σ) and Mean Wavelength (λ_0) are calculated.

Modifying Uncertainty Components

Fixed Points

Component	Value	Unit
1 Monochromator scale	0.01	nm
2 Reference detector	0.00018	nm
3 Scattering, polarisation	0.0006	nm
4 Out-of-band transmittance	0.002	nm
5 Drift	0.01	nm
6 Repeatability	0.0018	nm

Save

In-use Signal: S_{in}

Components

Component	Value	Unit
1 SSE	0.01	%
2 Non-linearity	0.005	%
3 Gain ratios	0.01	%
4 Ambient conditions	0.002	%
5 Drift	0.01	%
6 Repeatability	0.003	%

Name: ReC Save

Temperature: 2747.84 K Signal: 1.00886e-06

Temperature Uncertainties:

Component	Value	Unit
1 Total	350.0	mK

Signal Uncertainties:

Component	Value	Unit
1 Emissivity of fixed point	0.0	%
2 Ambient conditions	0.001	%
3 SSE	0.01	%
4 Gain ratios	0.01	%
5 Repeatability	0.006	%

Name: ReC Save

Temperature: 2747.84 K Signal: 1.00886e-06

Temperature Uncertainties:

Component	Value	Unit
1 Total	350.0	mK

Signal Uncertainties:

Component	Value	Unit
1 Emissivity of fixed point	0.0	%
2 Ambient conditions	0.001	%
3 SSE	0.01	%
4 Gain ratios	0.01	%
5 Repeatability	0.006	%

Run ITS 90

Fixed Points:

Select	Name	Temperature
1	CoC	1597.39 K
2	Cu	1357.802 K
3	Re	
4	Ru	
5	W	

Fixed Points

1	Monochromator scale
2	Reference detector
3	Scattering, polarisation
4	Out-of-band transmittance
5	Drift
6	Repeatability

Delete Fixed Point
Add Fixed Point
Save As

After pressing the Save as button, the corresponding fixed point data can be saved to the computer.

After the changes are made, save button of the relevant component is pressed. Thus, the changes made are saved in the memory of the software.

In the Fixed point tab, the uncertainty components can be changed easily.

Making a Calibration

Fixed points to be calibrated are selected. According to the selected fixed point number, the software determines which calibration it will perform (n=1,2,3 or n>3).

Fixed Points:

When the ITS 90 button is clicked, the calculations are changed according to the ITS 90 standard (Only for n=1).

The software performs the calibration and calculates the uncertainties.

Analyzing the Uncertainty Values of Different Temperatures

	1	2	3	4	5
Uncertainty Component	Values	Cu(1357.802 K)	(1597.39 K)	(1357.802 K)	(2000.0 K)
Standard Deviation		Temp.Unc.(K)	Temp.Unc.(K)	Temp.Unc.(K)	Temp.Unc.(K)
Total	0.00014 nm	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
MeanWavelength		0.000	0.006	0.000	0.021
Monochromator scale	0.01 nm	0.000	0.004	0.000	0.015
Reference detector	0.00018 nm	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Scattering, polarisation	0.0006 nm	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001
Out-of-band transmittance	0.002 nm	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.003
Drift	0.01 nm	0.000	0.004	0.000	0.015
Repeatability	0.0018 nm	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.003
In-Use Signal		0.015	0.021	0.015	0.033
SSE	0.01 %	0.008	0.012	0.008	0.018
Non-linearity	0.005 %	0.004	0.006	0.004	0.009
Gain ratios	0.01 %	0.008	0.012	0.008	0.018
Ambient conditions	0.002 %	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.004
Drift	0.01 %	0.008	0.012	0.008	0.018
Repeatability	0.003 %	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.005
T1		0.080	0.111	0.080	0.174
Total	80.0 mK	0.080	0.111	0.080	0.174
S1		0.009	0.012	0.009	0.019
Emissivity of fixed point	0.01 %	0.008	0.012	0.008	0.018
Ambient conditions	0.002 %	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.004
Repeatability	0.003 %	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.005
Combined Uncertainty		0.082	0.114	0.082	0.179

In the Table tab, the uncertainty component of the fixed points used in the calibration and the constant temperatures added to the table can be seen.

After clicking the mouse right button and clicking the Add Component button, the uncertainty values to be displayed in the table are entered.

	0.004	0.015	0.033
	0.001	0.003	0.003
	0.021	0.015	0.033
	0.012	0.008	0.018
	0.006	0.004	0.009

The table can be exported as an excel file by right-clicking and exporting.

Exporting Data

To export the calibration and its results, there are Export Calibration and Export Uncertainty options in the file menu.

Demo of the software

Thank You..

